

中国的蘑菇中毒事件(2019-2023)——基于中国疾控中心报告的数据清单

Mushroom poisoning in China (2019-2023)—Data listing based on CDC reports

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Text

在中国, 蘑菇中毒是备受关注的食品安全事件. 为便于科普宣传, 我们基于中国疾病预防控制中心的历年报告 (Li et al. 2020-2024) 整理了国内 2019 年至 2023 年已知的蘑菇中毒事件有关数据, 制成以下七表, 供参考.

In China, mushroom poisoning is a food safety issue of high attention. Towards the popularization of science, we sorted and analyzed the related data of known mushroom poisoning incidents in China from 2019 to 2023 based on the annual reports of Chinese Center for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), presenting the seven tables for reference as follows.

表 1 呈现了各症状类型 (基于中毒后出现的主要症状分七种症状类型, 即急性肝损害型 (Acute liver failure)、急性肾衰竭型 (Acute kidney failure)、横纹肌溶解型 (Rhabdomyolysis)、溶血型 (Hemolysis)、胃肠炎型 (Gastroenteritis)、神经精神型 (Psycho-neurological disorder) 和光过敏性皮炎型 (Photosensitive dermatitis); 不属于这七类型者纳入未定型 (Unclassified), 通常是因为数据不足尚不能定型; 毒蘑菇以其主要导致的某种或某些症状类型为毒性类型) 的基本数据. 死亡人数最多的前三种类型依次是急性肝损

害型、横纹肌溶解型和急性肾衰竭型，分别主要由鹅膏属檐托鹅膏组 (*Amanita* sect. *Phalloideae*) 物种、亚稀褶红菇 (*Russula subnigricans*) 及其近缘种、鹅膏属残鳞鹅膏组 (*Amanita* sect. *Roanokenses*) 物种造成；这些类群应得到野蘑菇采食者和有关医务工作者的特别重视，一种可考虑的做法是连属于这些类群的食用菌都要避免采食，包括草鸡枞 (*Amanita caojizong*) (图 1-2) 和“火炭菌”(可食的菌盖黑色色调的红菇属 (*Russula*) 物种)。此外，主要由卷边桩菇 (*Paxillus involutus*) 及其近缘种造成的溶血型也具有高死亡率，但发生的案例较少。胃肠炎型和神经精神型很少造成死亡案例。剩余其他类型则未报道死亡案例。

Table 1 presents the basic data of each symptom type (classified according to the main symptom in poisoning, including seven types, viz. Acute liver failure, Acute kidney failure, Rhabdomyolysis, Hemolysis, Gastroenteritis, Psycho-neurological disorder, and Photosensitive dermatitis; those not included in these types are sorted as Unclassified, generally due to the lack of data; a poisonous species that mainly causes one or more symptom types adapting the symptom type(s) as its toxicity type(s)). The top three types causing most deaths are Acute liver failure, Rhabdomyolysis and Acute kidney failure, successively, mainly caused by species of *Amanita* sect. *Phalloideae*, *Russula subnigricans* and its allies, and species of *Amanita* sect. *Roanokenses*, respectively; these taxa should be specifically noticed by wild mushroom hunters and relevant medical workers. A possible choice is to avoid hunting and eating even edible species in these taxa, including *Amanita caojizong* (Figures 1 & 2) and “huotanjun” (edible *Russula* species with a blackish pileus). Additionally, the type Hemolysis mainly caused by *Paxillus involutus* and its allies also presents a high fatality, but it occurred in fewer cases. The types Gastroenteritis and Psycho-neurological disorder rarely caused deaths. No deaths were reported for the remaining types.

▲ 图 1. 草鸡枞 (*Amanita caojizong*) 是以造成急性肾衰竭型中毒而闻名的鹅膏属残鳞鹅膏组 (*Amanita* sect. *Roanokenses*) 中罕有的可食物种，因此面临着尴尬的局面——一些剧毒或很可能有毒的物种和它在形态上极为相似，如假褐云斑鹅膏 (*A. pseudoporphyria*)。基于草鸡枞的原始描述 (Cui et al. 2018)，它和假褐云斑鹅膏可靠的形态学区别在显微结构中。图示蘑菇爱好者两块脆薯饼 (网名) 采集自浙江省的两份标本：HTBM1117 (草鸡枞) 和 HTBM1118 (假褐云斑鹅膏)，经分子标记 ITS 和 nrLSU 鉴定；它们分别采集自相距仅十多米的两处，暗示着这两个物种有混合生长的可能；照片由两块脆薯饼拍摄。

Figure 1. In the *Amanita* sect. *Roanokenses* (known for causing Acute Kidney Failure), the edible species *A. caojizong* is a dramatic member, so it has to face with an awkward situation—Some fatal (such as *A. pseudoporphyria*) or probably fatal species are

morphologically very similar to it. Based on the protologue of *A. caojizong* (Cui et al. 2018), the reliable morphological differences between the two species are in microstructure. This figure presents two specimens collected by the mycology hobbyist Two crisp hash browns (Screen name) from Zhejiang Province: HTBM1117 (*A. caojizong*) and HTBM1118 (*A. pseudoporphyria*), identified by molecular markers ITS and nrLSU; they were collected from two sites just over 10 meters apart, implying that the two species may mixedly grow together; photos by Two crisp hash browns.

▲ 图 2. 食用菌草鸡枞 (*Amanita caojizong*) 的迷因概念图, 包含了目前 (截至 2024 年 6 月 14 日) 在中国已发现的彼此相似的八个物种. 这类迷因在中国互联网上广泛传播, 暗示着公众对采食草鸡枞的安全性的担忧. 图源: 草鸡枞 (HTBM1117) 和假褐云斑鹅膏 (HTBM1118) 由两块脆薯饼 (网名) 拍摄, 隐花青鹅膏 (HTBM1006) 由陈斌拍摄, 肉托鹅膏 (HTBM1588)、暗棕鹅膏 (HTBM0460) 和假草鸡枞 (HTBM1275) 由刘振超拍摄, 淡粉褶鹅膏 (HKAS101403, 主模式) 和假隐花青鹅膏 (HKAS83470, 主模式) 摘自 Cui et al. (2018); 图中所有标本至少经分子标记 nrLSU 鉴定.

Figure 2. Concept diagram of the meme of the edible mushroom *Amanita caojizong* (commonly known as “caojizong” in Chinese), including eight species similar to each other that have been discovered in China to date (June 14, 2024). Such meme is widely circulated on Chinese Internet, implying the public concerns regarding the safety of hunting and eating *A. caojizong*. Photo sources: *A. caojizong* (HTBM1117) and *A. pseudoporphyria* (HTBM1118) by Two crisp hash browns (Screen name), *A. manginiana* (HTBM1006) by Bin Chen, *A. modesta* (HTBM1588), *A. atrobrunnea* (HTBM0460) and the undescribed *Amanita* sp. (HTBM1275) by Zhen-Chao Liu, *A. roseolifolia* (HKAS101403, holotype) and *A. pseudomanginiana* (HKAS83470, holotype) reproduced from Cui et al. (2018); all specimens were molecularly identified with markers at least nrLSU.

表 2-3 呈现了出现死亡案例的误食类型 (所误食蘑菇的物种组合, 例如只误食了致命鹅膏

(*Amanita exitialis*) 或同时误食了灰花纹鹅膏 (*A. fuliginea*) 和黄盖鹅膏 (*A. subjunquillea*) 等), 大多包含以上提到的物种. 值得注意的是, 还有两种小型蘑菇也造成了较多中毒和死亡案例: (1) 条盖盔孢伞 (*Galerina sulciceps*), 可能因其形似可食的蜡蘑属 (*Laccaria*) 物种 (俗称“皮条菌”等) 而经常被误采; (2) 肉褐鳞环柄菇 (*Lepiota brunneoincarnata*), 可能因其形似可食的香菇 (*Lentinula edodes*) 而经常被误采. 此外, 一个网隙硬皮马勃近似种 (*Scleroderma* aff. *areolatum*) 和土红鹅膏 (*Amanita rufoferruginea*) 也造成了死亡案例, 警示着胃肠炎型和神经精神型物种同样可能有致命危险.

Tables 2 & 3 present the ingestion types (Combination of ingested species, such as only *Amanita exitialis* or both *A. fuliginea* and *A. subjunquillea*, etc.) with deaths, mostly including the above-mentioned species. Notably, two species of small-sized mushrooms also caused many cases of poisoning and deaths: (1) *Galerina sulciceps*, may be mistakenly collected because of its resemblance to edible *Laccaria* species (commonly known as “pitiaojun” etc. in Chinese); and (2) *Lepiota brunneoincarnata*, may be mistakenly collected because of its resemblance to edible *Lentinula edodes* (shiitake). Additionally, *Scleroderma* aff. *areolatum* and *Amanita rufoferruginea* also caused deaths, warning that species causing Gastroenteritis and Psycho-neurological disorder may also be fatal.

表 4 呈现了中毒人数达 20 及以上的误食类型, 指示了最常被误食的毒蘑菇类群. 应特别注意其中七个中毒人数超过了 100 的误食类型: (1) 大青褶伞 (*Chlorophyllum molybdites*) (1107 人中毒), 可能因其在城市绿地中产量较大、担子果引人注目而被误采; (2) 日本红菇复合群 (*Russula japonica* complex) (425 人中毒; 注意在 Li et al. (2024) 中, 该复合群被细分为多个隐形种录入数据, 因此“日本红菇复合群”名下的真实中毒人数应为 425+141(Li et al. 2024)=566), 可能因其在森林中产量较大、担子果引人注目而被误采; (3) 近江粉褶蕈 (*Entoloma omiense*) (199 人中毒), 可能因其形似可食的蚁巢伞属 (*Termitomyces*) 物种 (俗称“鸡枞”等) 而经常被误采; (4) 亚稀褶红菇 (*Russula subnigricans*) (197 人中毒), 可能因其形似可食的菌盖黑色色调的红菇属 (*Russula*) 物种 (俗称“火炭菌”等) 而经常被误采; (5) 致命鹅膏 (*Amanita exitialis*) (130 人中毒), 可能因其形似可食的草菇属 (*Volvariella*) 物种和蚁巢伞属 (*Termitomyces*) 物种 (俗称“鸡枞”等) 而经常被误采; (6) 肉褐鳞环柄菇 (*Lepiota brunneoincarnata*) (130 人中毒), 可能因其形似可食的香菇 (*Lentinula edodes*) 而经常被误采; (7) 球基鹅膏 (*Amanita subglobosa*) (109 人中毒), 可能因其在森林中产量较大、担子果引人注目而被误采. 加强对这些毒蘑菇类群的科普宣传, 可能是降低未来中毒事件数量的关键举措.

Table 4 presents the ingestion types with ≥ 20 patients, indicating the most commonly ingested poisonous taxa. Seven ingestion types with more than 100 patients should be given special attention: (1) *Chlorophyllum molybdites* (1107 patients), may be mistakenly collected because of its high yield in urban green areas and remarkable basidiomata; (2) *Russula japonica* complex (425 patients; note that in Li et al. (2024), this complex was divided into several cryptic species for data recording, so the proper number of patients under the name “*Russula japonica* complex” should be 425+141(Li et al. 2024)=566), may be mistakenly collected because of its high yield in forests and remarkable basidiomata; (3) *Entoloma omiense* (199 patients), may be mistakenly collected because of its resemblance to edible *Termitomyces* species (commonly known as “jizong” etc. in Chinese); (4) *Russula subnigricans* (197 patients), may be mistakenly collected because of its resemblance to edible *Russula* species with a blackish pileus

(commonly known as “huotanjun” etc. in Chinese); (5) *Amanita exitialis* (130 patients), may be mistakenly collected because of its resemblance to edible *Volvariella* species and *Termitomyces* species (commonly known as “jizong” etc. in Chinese); (6) *Lepiota brunneoincarnata* (130 patients), may be mistakenly collected because of its resemblance to edible *Lentinula edodes* (shiitake); and (7) *Amanita subglobosa* (109 patients), may be mistakenly collected because of its high yield in forests and remarkable basidiomata. Stepping up the science popularization of these poisonous taxa could be the key to reduce the number of poisoning incidents in the future.

表 5 呈现了不含目前作为毒菌记载的物种的误食类型。大多数情况下，这是因为“中毒者”混吃了真正有毒的物种但调查时没有被检出。少数情况下，可能是因为“中毒者”的特殊体质出现了过敏或是其他情况，或是这些物种确实有毒但以往被错误记载了。表中“中毒人数”最多的前两个误食类型值得一提：(1) 原始报道于 Li et al. (2023) 中食用了牛肝菌干品的一个中毒案例，仅检出了可食的白牛肝菌 (*Boletus bainiugan*) 和网盖牛肝菌 (*B. reticuloceps*)，涉及 28 名中毒者；应当指出的是，将混合采集的多种牛肝菌制成干品在中国是相当常见的现象，因此很可能是该案例的干品中还混杂了未被检出的有毒牛肝菌物种；(2) 多个仅检出了可食的云南硬皮马勃 (*Scleroderma yunnanense*) 的中毒案例，涉及 16 名中毒者；应当指出的是，与云南硬皮马勃在形态上极为相似的有毒物种——光硬皮马勃 (*S. cepa*) 在中国也是常见种 (原始描述 Zhang et al. (2013) 甚至仅报道了两者在显微结构上的区别；图 3)，并且与前者存在重合的分布区域，造成 82 人中毒 (表 6)；因此如果案例中混杂了光硬皮马勃将很难检出，即使对案发后保留的每一个独立的担子果都进行鉴定 (如果光硬皮马勃的担子果恰好被吃完了呢?)。

Table 5 presents the ingestion types without species currently recorded as poisonous. In most cases, this is because the patients mixed some truly poisonous species into the meal but was not detected in the investigation. In a few cases, it is because allergies or other conditions due to the particular constitution of the patients, or the species is indeed poisonous but has been misdocumented currently. The top two ingestion types with the most patients are notable: (1) A case originally reported in Li et al. (2023) ingesting dried boletes, but only two edible species *Boletus bainiugan* and *B. reticuloceps* were detected, involving 28 patients; notably, making dried products of mixedly collected boletes is quite common in China, so probably the dried products in this case included mixed poisonous bolete species not detected; (2) Several poisoning cases with only edible *Scleroderma yunnanense* detected, involving 16 patients; notably, *S. cepa*—a poisonous species presenting morphology very similar to *S. yunnanense* (even only differences in microstructure were reported in the protologue of *S. yunnanense* (Zhang et al. (2013); Figure 3), is a common species in China and shows a overlapping distribution area with the latter, causing 82 patients (Table 6); therefore, it is rather difficult to detect the mixed *S. cepa* in a poisoning case with *S. yunnanense*, even if each basidioma retained after the incident is identified (What can you do if the basidiomata of *S. cepa* have just been totally ingested by the patients?).

▲ 图 3. 形态上极为相似的有毒的光硬皮马勃 (*Scleroderma cepa*) (A1–A2) 和可食的云南硬皮马勃 (*S. yunnanense*) (B1–B3), 经分子标记 ITS 和 nrLSU 鉴定. 基于我们的经验, 两者宏观上的最可靠的区别似乎在于前者的包被通常更薄、包被表面的鳞片通常更细密而平滑, 而后的包被通常更厚、包被表面的鳞片通常更大块而粗糙, 但仍有相当大的重合范围和不稳定性. 标本源: A1 自 HTBM0366, A2 自 HTBM0414, B1–B2 自 HTBM0311, B3 自 HTBM0393.

Figure 3. Morphologically similar poisonous *Scleroderma cepa* (A1–A2) and edible *S. yunnanense* (B1–B3), identified by molecular markers ITS and nrLSU. Based on our experience, the most reliable macroscopic differences between the two species seems to be: the former usually presents thinner peridium plus finer and smoother squamules, while the latter usually presents thicker peridium plus lumpier and rougher squamules; notably, there is still a considerable range of overlapping and instability between these “differences”. Specimen sources: A1 from HTBM0366, A2 from HTBM0414, B1–B2 from HTBM0311, B3 from HTBM0393.

表 6 呈现了所有误食类型, 包含 2019–2023 年中国蘑菇中毒事件中的所有关键数据.

Table 6 presents all ingestion types, including all key data in mushroom poisoning incidents in China from 2019 to 2023.

表 7 呈现了 2020–2023 年中国各省级行政区蘑菇中毒事件的基本数据 (2019 年无此数据).

Table 7 presents the basic data of mushroom poisoning incidents in each province-level administrative division in China from 2020 to 2023 (no such data for 2019).

请注意: (1) 我们对原始数据进行了必要的修订, 例如 (a) 将“aff. (近似)”和“cf. (参照...)”统

一表述为“aff. (近似)”、(b) 将不同年份报道的多个同形误食类型合并为一个误食类型 (如将 Li et al. (2022) 和 Li et al. (2023) 中都报道了的“一个盔孢伞属未定种 (*Galerina* sp.)”合并为“多个盔孢伞属未定种 (*Galerina* spp.)”) 和 (c) 去除明显为通常不具普遍性的由过敏等因素造成的“中毒案例”(如香菇皮炎 (Shiitake dermatitis) 等) 等; (2) 我们在本文中使用的“毒蘑菇”概念是相对广义的, 包括大型真菌中通常具普遍性的对多数人表现生化或物理毒性的物种, 但不包括通常不具普遍性的导致部分人群过敏的物种 (另见 (1c)); (3) 本文呈现的数据为得到报道的数据, 通常小于实际数据; (4) 限于条件, 本文中的七表三图主要由第一作者和第二作者仅用了三天整理制作. 我们尽可能保证了准确性, 仍不能排除存在错误的可能. **我们建议读者应谨慎将这些内容应用于更严格的场景.**

Please note: (1) We revised the original data when necessary, such as (a) “aff. (affinis)” and “cf. (confer...)” were uniformly expressed as “aff.”, (b) several homomorphic ingestion types reported in different years were combined into a single ingestion type (such as the “*Galerina* sp.” both reported in Li et al. (2022) and Li et al. (2023) were combined as “*Galerina* spp.”), and (c) “poisoning cases” obviously caused by other factors such as allergies (such as Shiitake dermatitis, etc.) were removed, etc.; (2) The concept of “poisonous mushrooms” we refer to in this article is relatively a broad sense, including the macrofungal species usually of toxicity to most people from biochemical or physical origins, but not those usually only causing allergies in few people (see also (1c)); (3) The data presented in this article represents reported data, which is usually lower than actual data; (4) Limited to condition, the seven tables and three figures in this article were mainly compiled by the first author and the second author in only three days; although we have tried our best to ensure accuracy, the possibility of error cannot be ruled out. **We suggest readers to be cautious about applying these contents for use in more rigorous scenarios.**

▼ **表 1.** 2019–2023 年中国蘑菇中毒事件中各症状类型的基本数据; 按死亡人数降序排序.
Table 1. Basic data of each symptom type in mushroom poisoning incidents in China from 2019 to 2023, in descending order of Deaths.

症状类型 Symptom types	事件数 Incidents	中毒人数 Patients	死亡人数 Deaths	死亡率 Fatality
急性肝损害型 Acute Liver Failure	268	754	82	10.88%
横纹肌溶解型 Rhabdomyolysis	73	219	19	8.68%
急性肾衰竭型 Acute Kidney Failure	101	237	5	2.11%
溶血型 Hemolysis	5	5	2	40.00%
胃肠炎型 Gastroenteritis	1141	3003	2	0.07%
神经精神型 Psycho-neurological Disorder	283	844	1	0.12%
光过敏性皮炎型 Photosensitive dermatitis	5	10	0	0
未定型 Unclassified	107	276	0	0

▼ 表 2. 2019–2023 年中国蘑菇中毒事件中死亡案例的误食类型; 按死亡率降序排序.
Table 2. Ingestion types with deaths in mushroom poisoning incidents in China from 2019 to 2023, in descending order of Fatality.

误食类型 Ingestion types	事件数 Incidents	中毒人数 Patients	死亡人数 Deaths	死亡率 Fatality
致命鹅膏、臧氏鹅膏(未定)和一个鹅膏属未定种(未定) <i>Amanita exitialis</i> , <i>A. zangii</i> U & <i>Amanita</i> sp. U	1	1	1	100.00%
近淡玫红鹅膏、近灰花纹鹅膏、黑毛小塔氏菌(胃肠)、松林乳牛肝菌(食用、胃肠)、杵柄鹅膏(神经)、肺形侧耳(食用)和鲜艳乳菇(食用) <i>Amanita subpallidorosea</i> , <i>A. subfuliginea</i> , <i>Tapinella atrotomentosa</i> G, <i>Suillus pinetorum</i> E, G, <i>A. sinocitrina</i> P, <i>Pleurotus pulmonarius</i> E & <i>Lactarius vividus</i> E	1	2	2	100.00%
灰花纹鹅膏和黄盖鹅膏 <i>Amanita fuliginea</i> & <i>A. subjunquillea</i>	1	4	3	75.00%
拟灰花纹鹅膏、假褐云斑鹅膏(肾衰)、异味鹅膏(肾衰)、格纹鹅膏(神经)、一个鹅膏属未定种(未定)、多个红菇属未定种(未定)和致密红菇(食用) <i>Amanita fuligineoides</i> , <i>A. pseudoporphyria</i> AKF, <i>A. kotohiraensis</i> AKF, <i>A. fritillaria</i> P, <i>Amanita</i> sp. U, <i>Russula</i> spp. U & <i>Russula compacta</i> E	1	3	2	66.67%
一个鹅膏属未定种、褐环乳牛肝菌(食用、胃肠)、红汁乳菇(食用)和血红菇(食用) <i>Amanita</i> sp., <i>Suillus luteus</i> E, G, <i>Lactarius hatsudake</i> E & <i>Russula sanguinea</i> E	1	2	1	50.00%
一个鹅膏属未定种、黄盖堪多脆柄菇(神经)、一个蘑菇属未定种(未定)和一个红菇属未定种(未定) <i>Amanita</i> sp., <i>Candolleomyces candolleanus</i> P, <i>Agaricus</i> sp. U & <i>Russula</i> sp. U	1	2	1	50.00%
卷边桩菇 <i>Paxillus involutus</i>	5	5	2	40.00%
近淡玫红鹅膏 <i>Amanita subpallidorosea</i>	12	21	7	33.33%
网隙硬皮马勃近似种和云南硬皮马勃(食用) <i>Scleroderma</i> aff. <i>areolatum</i> & <i>S. yunnanense</i> E	1	9	2	22.22%
拟灰花纹鹅膏 <i>Amanita fuligineoides</i>	4	28	6	21.43%
淡玫红鹅膏近似种 <i>Amanita</i> aff. <i>pallidorosea</i>	2	5	1	20.00%
致命鹅膏 <i>Amanita exitialis</i>	45	130	23	17.69%
裂皮鹅膏 <i>Amanita rimosa</i>	11	44	7	15.91%
多个鹅膏属未定种 <i>Amanita</i> spp.	11	30	4	13.33%
条盖盔孢伞 <i>Galerina sulciceps</i>	36	99	12	12.12%
亚稀褶红菇 <i>Russula subnigricans</i>	64	197	19	9.64%
灰花纹鹅膏近似种 <i>Amanita</i> aff. <i>fuliginea</i>	4	14	1	7.14%
灰花纹鹅膏或裂皮鹅膏 <i>Amanita fuliginea</i> or <i>A. rimosa</i>	4	14	1	7.14%
肉褐鳞环柄菇 <i>Lepiota brunneoincarnata</i>	54	130	8	6.15%

... 待续 continued below

▼ 表 2. (续表)
Table 2. (continued)

误食类型 Ingestion types	事件数 Incidents	中毒人数 Patients	死亡人数 Deaths	死亡率 Fatality
假褐云斑鹅膏 <i>Amanita pseudoporphyria</i>	29	89	5	5.62%
淡玫红鹅膏 <i>Amanita pallidorosea</i>	13	27	1	3.70%
土红鹅膏 <i>Amanita rufoferruginea</i>	17	49	1	2.04%
黄盖鹅膏 <i>Amanita subjunquillea</i>	17	59	1	1.69%

▼ 表 3. 2019–2023 年中国蘑菇中毒事件中死亡案例的误食类型; 按死亡人数降序排序。
Table 3. Ingestion types with deaths in mushroom poisoning incidents in China from 2019 to 2023, in descending order of Deaths.

误食类型 Ingestion types	事件数 Incidents	中毒人数 Patients	死亡人数 Deaths	死亡率 Fatality
致命鹅膏 <i>Amanita exitialis</i>	45	130	23	17.69%
亚稀褶红菇 <i>Russula subnigricans</i>	64	197	19	9.64%
条盖盔孢伞 <i>Galerina sulciceps</i>	36	99	12	12.12%
肉褐鳞环柄菇 <i>Lepiota brunneoincarnata</i>	54	130	8	6.15%
近淡玫红鹅膏 <i>Amanita subpallidorosea</i>	12	21	7	33.33%
裂皮鹅膏 <i>Amanita rimosa</i>	11	44	7	15.91%
拟灰花纹鹅膏 <i>Amanita fuligineoides</i>	4	28	6	21.43%
假褐云斑鹅膏 <i>Amanita pseudoporphyria</i>	29	89	5	5.62%
灰花纹鹅膏和黄盖鹅膏 <i>Amanita fuliginea</i> & <i>A. subjunquillea</i>	1	4	3	75.00%
近淡玫红鹅膏、近灰花纹鹅膏、黑毛小塔氏菌(胃肠)、松林乳牛肝菌(食用、胃肠)、杵柄鹅膏(神经)、肺形侧耳(食用)和鲜艳乳菇(食用) <i>Amanita subpallidorosea</i> , <i>A. subfuliginea</i> , <i>Tapinella atrotomentosa</i> G, <i>Suillus pinetorum</i> E, G, <i>A. sinocitrina</i> P, <i>Pleurotus pulmonarius</i> E & <i>Lactarius vividus</i> E	1	2	2	100.00%
拟灰花纹鹅膏、假褐云斑鹅膏(肾衰)、异味鹅膏(肾衰)、格纹鹅膏(神经)、一个鹅膏属未定种(未定)、多个红菇属未定种(未定)和致密红菇(食用) <i>Amanita fuligineoides</i> , <i>A. pseudoporphyria</i> AKF, <i>A. kotohiraensis</i> AKF, <i>A. fritillaria</i> P, <i>Amanita</i> sp. U, <i>Russula</i> spp. U & <i>Russula compacta</i> E	1	3	2	66.67%
卷边桩菇 <i>Paxillus involutus</i>	5	5	2	40.00%
网隙硬皮马勃近似种和云南硬皮马勃(食用) <i>Scleroderma</i> aff. <i>areolatum</i> & <i>S. yunnanense</i> E	1	9	2	22.22%

... 待续 continued below

▼ 表 3. (续表)
Table 3. (continued)

误食类型 Ingestion types	事件数 Incidents	中毒人数 Patients	死亡人数 Deaths	死亡率 Fatality
致命鹅膏、臧氏鹅膏(未定)和一个鹅膏属未定种(未定) <i>Amanita exitialis</i> , <i>A. zangii</i> U & <i>Amanita</i> sp. U	1	1	1	100.00%
一个鹅膏属未定种、褐环乳牛肝菌(食用、胃肠)、红汁乳菇(食用)和血红菇(食用) <i>Amanita</i> sp., <i>Suillus luteus</i> E, G, <i>Lactarius hatsudake</i> E & <i>Russula sanguinea</i> E	1	2	1	50.00%
一个鹅膏属未定种、黄盖堪多脆柄菇(神精)、一个蘑菇属未定种(未定)和一个红菇属未定种(未定) <i>Amanita</i> sp., <i>Candolleomyces candolleanus</i> P, <i>Agaricus</i> sp. U & <i>Russula</i> sp. U	1	2	1	50.00%
淡玫红鹅膏近似种 <i>Amanita</i> aff. <i>pallidorosea</i>	2	5	1	20.00%
多个鹅膏属未定种 <i>Amanita</i> spp.	11	30	4	13.33%
灰花纹鹅膏近似种 <i>Amanita</i> aff. <i>fuliginea</i>	4	14	1	7.14%
灰花纹鹅膏或裂皮鹅膏 <i>Amanita fuliginea</i> or <i>A. rimosa</i>	4	14	1	7.14%
淡玫红鹅膏 <i>Amanita pallidorosea</i>	13	27	1	3.70%
土红鹅膏 <i>Amanita rufoferruginea</i>	17	49	1	2.04%
黄盖鹅膏 <i>Amanita subjunquillea</i>	17	59	1	1.69%

▼ 表 4. 2019-2023 年中国蘑菇中毒事件中中毒人数达 20 及以上的误食类型; 按中毒人数降序排序.

Table 4. Ingestion types with ≥20 patients in mushroom poisoning incidents in China from 2019 to 2023, in descending order of Patients.

误食类型 Ingestion types	事件数 Incidents	中毒人数 Patients	死亡人数 Deaths	死亡率 Fatality
大青褶伞 <i>Chlorophyllum molybdites</i>	534	1107	0	0
日本红菇复合群 <i>Russula japonica</i> complex	150	425	0	0
近江粉褶蕈 <i>Entoloma omiense</i>	68	199	0	0
亚稀褶红菇 <i>Russula subnigricans</i>	64	197	19	9.64%
致命鹅膏 <i>Amanita exitialis</i>	45	130	23	17.69%
肉褐鳞环柄菇 <i>Lepiota brunneoincarnata</i>	54	130	8	6.15%
球基鹅膏 <i>Amanita subglobosa</i>	33	109	0	0
条盖盔孢伞 <i>Galerina sulciceps</i>	36	99	12	12.12%

... 待续 continued below

▼ 表 4. (续表)
Table 4. (continued)

误食类型 Ingestion types	事件数 Incidents	中毒人数 Patients	死亡人数 Deaths	死亡率 Fatality
欧氏鹅膏 <i>Amanita oberwinklerana</i>	44	93	0	0
假褐云斑鹅膏 <i>Amanita pseudoporphyria</i>	29	89	5	5.62%
残托鹅膏有环变型 <i>Amanita sychnopyramis</i> f. <i>subannulata</i>	18	86	0	0
光硬皮马勃 <i>Scleroderma cepa</i>	24	82	0	0
变色龙裸伞 <i>Gymnopilus dilepis</i>	24	61	0	0
黄盖鹅膏 <i>Amanita subjunquillea</i>	17	59	1	1.69%
棕褶类脐菇 <i>Omphalotus guepiniformis</i>	12	57	0	0
灰花纹鹅膏 <i>Amanita fuliginea</i>	23	55	0	0
球盖青褶伞 <i>Chlorophyllum globosum</i>	14	50	0	0
多个粉褶蕈属未定种 <i>Entoloma</i> spp.	17	51	0	0
土红鹅膏 <i>Amanita rufoferruginea</i>	17	49	1	2.04%
日本红菇 <i>Russula japonica</i>	20	49	0	0
除独角龙弯颈霉(神精)、格纹鹅膏(神精)、黄环鹅膏、显鳞 鹅膏、黄边鹅膏、花脸金钱菌(食用)、粗柄大口蘑(食用) 和云南硬皮马勃(食用)外的其他蘑菇 (Li et al. (2020) 报道) Other mushrooms except <i>Tolypocladium dujiaolongae</i> P, <i>Amanita</i> <i>fritillaria</i> P, <i>A. citrinoannulata</i> , <i>A. clarisquamosa</i> , <i>A. hamadae</i> , <i>Collybia sordida</i> E, <i>Macrocybe crassa</i> E & <i>Scleroderma yunnanense</i> E (reported in Li et al. (2020))	12	46	0	0
假日本红菇 <i>Russula pseudojaponica</i>	11	45	0	0
裂皮鹅膏 <i>Amanita rimosa</i>	11	44	7	15.91%
一个类脐菇属未定种 <i>Omphalotus</i> sp.	4	44	0	0
日本红菇近似种 <i>Russula</i> aff. <i>japonica</i>	10	43	0	0
有毒异色牛肝菌 <i>Sutorius venenatus</i>	11	34	0	0
古巴裸盖菇 <i>Psilocybe cubensis</i>	13	32	0	0
多个鹅膏属未定种 <i>Amanita</i> spp.	11	30	4	13.33%
拟灰花纹鹅膏 <i>Amanita fuligineoides</i>	4	28	6	21.43%

... 待续 continued below

▼ 表 4. (续表)
Table 4. (continued)

误食类型 Ingestion types	事件数 Incidents	中毒人数 Patients	死亡人数 Deaths	死亡率 Fatality
白牛肝菌(食用)和网盖牛肝菌(食用) <i>Boletus bainiugan</i> E & <i>B. reticuloceps</i> E	1	28	0	0
小毒蝇鹅膏 <i>Amanita melleiceps</i>	8	27	0	0
淡玫红鹅膏 <i>Amanita pallidorosea</i>	13	27	1	3.70%
球盖青褶伞近似种 <i>Chlorophyllum</i> aff. <i>globosum</i>	7	25	0	0
变红青褶伞 <i>Chlorophyllum hortense</i>	11	24	0	0
大果薄瓢牛肝菌 <i>Baorangia major</i>	6	23	0	0
密褶裸脚伞 <i>Gymnopus densilamellatus</i>	5	23	0	0
发光类脐菇 <i>Omphalotus olearius</i>	5	23	0	0
中华红孔牛肝菌和褐网柄牛肝菌(食用) <i>Rubroboletus sinicus</i> & <i>Retiboletus fuscus</i> E	2	23	0	0
恶嗅歧盖伞近似种 <i>Inosperma</i> aff. <i>virosum</i>	4	22	0	0
兰茂牛肝菌(食用、神精) <i>Lanmaoa asiatica</i> E, P	17	22	0	0
近淡玫红鹅膏 <i>Amanita subpallidorosea</i>	12	21	7	33.33%
黑紫变黑牛肝菌 <i>Anthracoportus nigropurpureus</i>	10	21	0	0
毒粉褶蕈近似种 <i>Entoloma</i> aff. <i>sinuatum</i>	5	20	0	0
潮湿金钱菌、洁小菇、毒灰盖杯伞、簇生垂幕菇(胃肠)、多环鳞伞(胃肠)、栎裸脚伞(胃肠)、橙黄乳菇(胃肠)、梭孢环柄菇(未定)、乳白小囊皮伞(未定)、一个蜡蘑属未定种(未定)、蜜环菌(食用)和皱盖囊皮伞(食用) <i>Collybia humida</i> , <i>Mycena pura</i> , <i>Spodocybe venenata</i> , <i>Hypholoma fasciculare</i> G, <i>Pholiota multicingulata</i> G, <i>Gymnopus dryophilus</i> G, <i>Lactarius citrinus</i> G, <i>Lepiota magnispora</i> U, <i>Cystoderma lactea</i> U, <i>Lacaria</i> sp. U, <i>Armillaria mellea</i> E & <i>Cystoderma amianthinum</i> E	1	20	0	0

▼ 表 5. 2019–2023 年中国蘑菇中毒事件中不含目前作为毒菌记载的物种的误食类型; 按中毒人数降序排序.

Table 5. Ingestion types without species currently recorded as poisonous in mushroom poisoning incidents in China from 2019 to 2023, in descending order of Patients.

误食类型 Ingestion types	事件数 Incidents	中毒人数 Patients	死亡人数 Deaths	死亡率 Fatality
白牛肝菌(食用)和网盖牛肝菌(食用) <i>Boletus bainiugan</i> E & <i>B. reticuloceps</i> E	1	28	0	0
云南硬皮马勃(食用) <i>Scleroderma yunnanense</i> E	6	16	0	0

... 待续 continued below

▼ 表 5. (续表)
Table 5. (continued)

误食类型 Ingestion types	事件数 Incidents	中毒人数 Patients	死亡人数 Deaths	死亡率 Fatality
棕灰口蘑(食用) <i>Tricholoma terreum</i> E	6	10	0	0
彝食黄肉牛肝菌(食用) <i>Butyriboletus yicibus</i> E	2	6	0	0
壳状红菇(食用)和云南蜡蘑(食用) <i>Russula crustosa</i> E & <i>Laccaria yunnanensis</i> E	1	6	0	0
赭鳞蘑菇(食用) <i>Agaricus subrufescens</i> E	1	4	0	0
紫丁金钱菌(食用、药用) <i>Collybia nuda</i> E, M	1	4	0	0
中华丝膜菌(食用) <i>Cortinarius sinensis</i> E	2	4	0	0
巨大侧耳(食用) <i>Pleurotus giganteus</i> E	1	4	0	0
彩色豆马勃复合群(食用、药用) <i>Pisolithus arhizus</i> complex E, M	1	4	0	0
绿桂红菇近似种(食用) <i>Russula</i> aff. <i>viridicinnamomea</i> E	1	4	0	0
细绒盖牛肝菌(食用) <i>Xerocomus parvulus</i> E	1	4	0	0
四孢蘑菇(食用) <i>Agaricus campestris</i> E	3	3	0	0
假高大鹅膏(食用) <i>Amanita pseudoprinceps</i> E	2	3	0	0
高卢蜜环菌(食用) <i>Armillaria gallica</i> E	1	3	0	0
蜜环菌(食用) <i>Armillaria mellea</i> E	1	3	0	0
雪白拟鬼伞(食用) <i>Coprinopsis nivea</i> E	1	3	0	0
毛头鬼伞(食用) <i>Coprinus comatus</i> E	2	3	0	0
粗柄大口蘑(食用) <i>Macrocybe crassa</i> E	2	3	0	0
泡状鳞伞(食用、药用) <i>Pholiota spumosa</i> E, M	1	3	0	0
白盖红菇(食用) <i>Russula leucocarpa</i> E	1	3	0	0
皱环球盖菇(食用) <i>Stropharia rugosoannulata</i> E	3	3	0	0
巴西蘑菇(食用) <i>Agaricus blazei</i> E	1	2	0	0
高大鹅膏近似种(食用) <i>Amanita</i> aff. <i>princeps</i> E	1	2	0	0
白牛肝菌(食用) <i>Boletus bainiugan</i> E	1	2	0	0
酒红蜡蘑(食用) <i>Laccaria vinaceoavellanea</i> E	1	2	0	0

... 待续 continued below

▼ 表 5. (续表)
Table 5. (continued)

误食类型 Ingestion types	事件数 Incidents	中毒人数 Patients	死亡人数 Deaths	死亡率 Fatality
肉桂色乳菇(食用) <i>Lactarius cinnamomeus</i> E	1	2	0	0
薄囊多汁乳菇(食用) <i>Lactifluus tenuicystidiatus</i> E	1	2	0	0
巴氏白环蘑(食用) <i>Leucoagaricus barssii</i> E	1	2	0	0
黄孔新牛肝菌(食用) <i>Neoboletus flavidus</i> E	2	2	0	0
黄孔新牛肝菌(食用)和大孢地花孔菌(食用) <i>Neoboletus flavidus</i> E & <i>Albatrellus ellisii</i> E	1	2	0	0
褐网柄牛肝菌(食用) <i>Retiboletus fuscus</i> E	1	2	0	0
密褶红菇(食用) <i>Russula densifolia</i> E	1	2	0	0
林地蘑菇近似种(食用) <i>Agaricus</i> aff. <i>arvensis</i> E	1	1	0	0
杯形秃马勃(食用、药用) <i>Calvatia cyathiformis</i> E, M	1	1	0	0
大秃马勃(食用、药用) <i>Calvatia gigantea</i> E, M	1	1	0	0
花脸金钱菌(食用) <i>Collybia sordida</i> E	1	1	0	0
隐孔菌(药用) <i>Cryptoporus volvatus</i> M	1	1	0	0
网纹马勃复合群(食用、药用) <i>Lycoperdon perlatum</i> complex E, M	1	1	0	0
虎皮韧伞(食用) <i>Lentinus tigrinus</i> E	1	1	0	0
糙皮侧耳(食用) <i>Pleurotus ostreatus</i> E	1	1	0	0
肺形侧耳(食用) <i>Pleurotus pulmonarius</i> E	1	1	0	0
裂褶菌(食用、药用)、毛栓孔菌(药用)和乳白耙齿菌(药用) <i>Schizophyllum commune</i> E, M, <i>Trametes hirsuta</i> M & <i>Irpex lacteus</i> M	1	1	0	0
云南蚁巢伞(食用) <i>Termitomyces yunnanensis</i> E	1	1	0	0

▼ 表 6. 2019–2023 年中国蘑菇中毒事件中的所有误食类型概览; 按具体案例的症状类型归类, 每类下按分类群拉丁学名排序. 误食类型中若包含毒性类型与症状类型不合的分类群, 将脚注其毒性类型的缩写: 急性肝损害型=肝损、急性肾衰竭型=肾衰、横纹肌溶解型=溶肌、溶血型=溶血、胃肠炎型=胃肠、神经精神型=神经、光过敏性皮炎型=光敏、未定型=未定、可食用=食用、可药用=药用.

Table 6. All ingestion types in mushroom poisoning incidents in China from 2019 to 2023, classified according to the symptom types in cases and ordered according to the Latin scientific name of taxa. If an ingestion type contains taxa with toxicity type(s) not consistent with the symptom type, the abbreviation the toxicity type(s) of the taxa will be footnoted (Acute liver failure=ALF, Acute kidney failure=AKF, Rhabdomyolysis=R, Hemolysis=H, Gastroenteritis=G, Psycho-neurological Disorder=P, Photosensitive dermatitis=PD, Unclassified=U, Edible=E, Medicinal=M).

误食类型 Ingestion types	事件数 Incidents	中毒人数 Patients	死亡人数 Deaths	死亡率 Fatality
急性肝损害型 Acute Liver Failure	268	754	82	10.88%
致命鹅膏 <i>Amanita exitialis</i>	45	130	23	17.69%
致命鹅膏和拟灰花纹鹅膏 <i>Amanita exitialis</i> & <i>A. fuligineoides</i>	1	4	0	0
致命鹅膏、臧氏鹅膏(未定)和一个鹅膏属未定种(未定) <i>Amanita exitialis</i> , <i>A. zangii</i> U & <i>Amanita</i> sp. U	1	1	1	100.00%
致命鹅膏近似种 <i>Amanita</i> aff. <i>exitialis</i>	2	6	0	0
灰花纹鹅膏 <i>Amanita fuliginea</i>	23	55	0	0
灰花纹鹅膏和格纹鹅膏(神经) <i>Amanita fuliginea</i> & <i>A. fritillaria</i> P	3	9	0	0
灰花纹鹅膏、格纹鹅膏(神经)和多个红菇属未定种(未定) <i>Amanita fuliginea</i> , <i>A. fritillaria</i> P & <i>Russula</i> spp. U	1	1	0	0
灰花纹鹅膏和拟卵盖鹅膏(肾衰) <i>Amanita fuliginea</i> & <i>A. neoovoidea</i> AKF	1	2	0	0
灰花纹鹅膏和欧氏鹅膏(肾衰) <i>Amanita fuliginea</i> & <i>A. oberwinklerana</i> AKF	2	7	0	0
灰花纹鹅膏和假褐云斑鹅膏(肾衰) <i>Amanita fuliginea</i> & <i>A. pseudoporphyria</i> AKF	2	3	0	0
灰花纹鹅膏和黄盖鹅膏 <i>Amanita fuliginea</i> & <i>A. subjunquillea</i>	1	4	3	75.00%
灰花纹鹅膏近似种 <i>Amanita</i> aff. <i>fuliginea</i>	4	14	1	7.14%
灰花纹鹅膏或裂皮鹅膏 <i>Amanita fuliginea</i> or <i>A. rimosa</i>	4	14	1	7.14%
拟灰花纹鹅膏 <i>Amanita fuligineoides</i>	4	28	6	21.43%
拟灰花纹鹅膏、假褐云斑鹅膏(肾衰)、异味鹅膏(肾衰)、格纹鹅膏(神经)、一个鹅膏属未定种(未定)、多个红菇属未定种(未定)和致密红菇(食用) <i>Amanita fuligineoides</i> , <i>A. pseudoporphyria</i> AKF, <i>A. kotohiraensis</i> AKF, <i>A. fritillaria</i> P, <i>Amanita</i> sp. U, <i>Russula</i> spp. U & <i>Russula compacta</i> E	1	3	2	66.67%

... 待续 continued below

▼ 表 6. (续表)
Table 6. (continued)

误食类型 Ingestion types	事件数 Incidents	中毒人数 Patients	死亡人数 Deaths	死亡率 Fatality
拟灰花纹鹅膏、假褐云斑鹅膏(肾衰)和黄蜡鹅膏(食用) <i>Amanita fuligineoides</i> , <i>A. pseudoporphyria</i> AKF & <i>A. kitamagotake</i> E	1	2	0	0
淡玫红鹅膏 <i>Amanita pallidorosea</i>	13	27	1	3.70%
淡玫红鹅膏和格纹鹅膏(神经) <i>Amanita pallidorosea</i> & <i>A. fritillaria</i> P	1	2	0	0
淡玫红鹅膏和杵柄鹅膏(神经) <i>Amanita pallidorosea</i> & <i>A. sinocitrina</i> P	1	1	0	0
淡玫红鹅膏近似种 <i>Amanita</i> aff. <i>pallidorosea</i>	2	5	1	20.00%
裂皮鹅膏 <i>Amanita rimosa</i>	11	44	7	15.91%
裂皮鹅膏和肉褐鳞环柄菇 <i>Amanita rimosa</i> & <i>Lepiota brunneoincarnata</i>	1	4	0	0
近灰花纹鹅膏 <i>Amanita subfuliginea</i>	2	5	0	0
黄盖鹅膏 <i>Amanita subjunquillea</i>	17	59	1	1.69%
黄盖鹅膏和欧氏鹅膏(肾衰) <i>Amanita subjunquillea</i> & <i>A. oberwinklerana</i> AKF	1	2	0	0
黄盖鹅膏、淡玫红鹅膏、欧氏鹅膏(肾衰)、簇生垂幕菇(胃肠)、球基蘑菇(胃肠)、中华双环蘑菇(胃肠)、格纹鹅膏(神经)、北京蘑菇(未定)、一个兰茂牛肝菌属未定种(未定)、卷毛蘑菇(食用)和紫丁香金钱菌(食用、药用) <i>Amanita subjunquillea</i> , <i>A. pallidorosea</i> , <i>A. oberwinklerana</i> AKF, <i>Hypholoma fasciculare</i> G, <i>Agaricus abruptibulbus</i> G, <i>A. sinoplacomycetes</i> G, <i>Amanita fritillaria</i> P, <i>Agaricus beijingensis</i> U, <i>Lanmaoa</i> sp. U, <i>Agaricus flocculosipes</i> E & <i>Collybia nuda</i> E, G	1	5	0	0
黄盖鹅膏、密褶裸脚伞(胃肠)、中华灰褐纹口蘑(胃肠)、红褐鹅膏(神经)、多个红菇属未定种(未定)、泡状鳞伞(食用、药用)、西伯利亚乳牛肝菌(食用、胃肠)和威氏齿菌(食用) <i>Amanita subjunquillea</i> , <i>Gymnopus densilamellatus</i> G, <i>Tricholoma sinoportentosum</i> G, <i>Amanita orsonii</i> P, <i>Russula</i> spp. U, <i>Pholiota spumosa</i> E, M, <i>Suillus sibiricus</i> E, G & <i>Hydnum vesterholtii</i> E	1	6	0	0
黄盖鹅膏、格纹鹅膏(神经)、乌村乳菇(胃肠)和卷毛蘑菇(食用) <i>Amanita subjunquillea</i> , <i>A. fritillaria</i> P, <i>Lactarius oomsisiensis</i> G & <i>Agaricus flocculosipes</i> E	1	2	0	0
近淡玫红鹅膏 <i>Amanita subpallidorosea</i>	12	21	7	33.33%
近淡玫红鹅膏、白绒多汁乳菇(胃肠)和橙黄鹅膏(神经) <i>Amanita subpallidorosea</i> , <i>Lactifluus puberulus</i> G & <i>Amanita citrina</i> P	1	3	0	0
近淡玫红鹅膏、近灰花纹鹅膏、黑毛小塔氏菌(胃肠)、松林乳牛肝菌(食用、胃肠)、杵柄鹅膏(神经)、肺形侧耳(食用)和鲜艳乳菇(食用) <i>Amanita subpallidorosea</i> , <i>A. subfuliginea</i> , <i>Tapinella atrotomentosa</i> G, <i>Suillus pinetorum</i> E, G, <i>A. sinocitrina</i> P, <i>Pleurotus pulmonarius</i> E & <i>Lactarius vividus</i> E	1	2	2	100.00%

... 待续 continued below

▼ 表 6. (续表)
Table 6. (continued)

误食类型 Ingestion types	事件数 Incidents	中毒人数 Patients	死亡人数 Deaths	死亡率 Fatality
一个鹅膏属未定种、褐环乳牛肝菌(食用、胃肠)、红汁乳菇(食用)和血红菇(食用) <i>Amanita</i> sp., <i>Suillus luteus</i> E, G, <i>Lactarius hatsudake</i> E & <i>Russula sanguinea</i> E	1	2	1	50.00%
一个鹅膏属未定种、黄盖堪多脆柄菇(神经)、一个蘑菇属未定种(未定)和一个红菇属未定种(未定) <i>Amanita</i> sp., <i>Candolleomyces candolleanus</i> P, <i>Agaricus</i> sp. U & <i>Russula</i> sp. U	1	2	1	50.00%
多个鹅膏属未定种 <i>Amanita</i> spp.	11	30	4	13.33%
条盖盔孢伞 <i>Galerina sulciceps</i>	36	99	12	12.12%
多个盔孢伞属未定种 <i>Galerina</i> spp.	2	19	0	0
肉褐鳞环柄菇 <i>Lepiota brunneoincarnata</i>	54	130	8	6.15%
肉褐鳞环柄菇和栎裸脚伞(胃肠) <i>Lepiota brunneoincarnata</i> & <i>Gymnopus dryophilus</i> G	1	1	0	0
急性肾衰竭型 Acute Kidney Failure	101	237	5	2.11%
赤脚鹅膏 <i>Amanita gymnopus</i>	3	4	0	0
异味鹅膏 <i>Amanita kotohiraensis</i>	1	2	0	0
拟卵盖鹅膏 <i>Amanita neoovoidea</i>	9	12	0	0
欧氏鹅膏 <i>Amanita oberwinklerana</i>	44	93	0	0
欧氏鹅膏和假褐云斑鹅膏 <i>Amanita oberwinklerana</i> & <i>A. pseudoporphyria</i>	3	6	0	0
欧氏鹅膏、格纹鹅膏(神经)、和黄丛毛蘑菇(未定)和香亚环乳菇(食用) <i>Amanita oberwinklerana</i> , <i>A. fritillaria</i> P, <i>Agaricus luteofibrillosus</i> U & <i>Lactarius subzonarius</i> E	1	2	0	0
欧氏鹅膏和假球基鹅膏近似种(神经) <i>Amanita oberwinklerana</i> & <i>A. aff. ibotengutake</i> P	1	1	0	0
欧氏鹅膏近似种 <i>Amanita</i> aff. <i>oberwinklerana</i>	1	3	0	0
假褐云斑鹅膏 <i>Amanita pseudoporphyria</i>	29	89	5	5.62%
假褐云斑鹅膏和日本红菇复合群(胃肠) <i>Amanita pseudoporphyria</i> & <i>Russula japonica</i> complex G	2	6	0	0
假褐云斑鹅膏和格纹鹅膏(神经) <i>Amanita pseudoporphyria</i> & <i>A. fritillaria</i> P	1	4	0	0
假褐云斑鹅膏和黄白乳牛肝菌(食用、胃肠) <i>Amanita pseudoporphyria</i> & <i>Suillus placidus</i> E, G	1	3	0	0
假褐云斑鹅膏近似种 <i>Amanita</i> aff. <i>pseudoporphyria</i>	5	12	0	0

... 待续 continued below

▼ 表 6. (续表)
Table 6. (continued)

误食类型 Ingestion types	事件数 Incidents	中毒人数 Patients	死亡人数 Deaths	死亡率 Fatality
横纹肌溶解型 Rhabdomyolysis	73	219	19	8.68%
亚稀褶红菇 <i>Russula subnigricans</i>	64	197	19	9.64%
亚稀褶红菇和日本红菇复合群(胃肠) <i>Russula subnigricans</i> & <i>R. japonica</i> complex G	1	4	0	0
亚稀褶红菇、日本红菇(胃肠)和斑柄红菇(胃肠) <i>Russula subnigricans</i> , <i>R. japonica</i> G & <i>R. punctipes</i> G	1	2	0	0
亚稀褶红菇和棱柱孢粉褶蕈(未定) <i>Russula subnigricans</i> & <i>Entoloma prismaticum</i> U	1	2	0	0
亚稀褶红菇和一个红菇属未定种(未定) <i>Russula subnigricans</i> & <i>Russula</i> sp. U	1	1	0	0
亚稀褶红菇、一个红菇属未定种(未定)、中华多汁乳菇(食用)、假致密红菇(食用)、红边绿红菇(食用)和细绒盖牛肝菌(食用) <i>Russula subnigricans</i> , <i>Russula</i> sp. U, <i>Lactifluus sinensis</i> E, <i>Russula pseudocompacta</i> E, <i>R. viridirubrolimbata</i> E & <i>Xerocomus parvulus</i> E	1	2	0	0
亚稀褶红菇和烟色红菇(食用) <i>Russula subnigricans</i> & <i>R. adusta</i> E	2	3	0	0
亚稀褶红菇、密褶红菇和烟色红菇近似种 <i>Russula subnigricans</i> , <i>R. densifolia</i> E & <i>R. aff. nigricans</i> E	1	7	0	0
油口蘑和一个口蘑属未定种(未定) <i>Tricholoma equestre</i> & <i>Tricholoma</i> sp. U	1	1	0	0
溶血型 Hemolysis	5	5	2	40.00%
卷边桩菇 <i>Paxillus involutus</i>	5	5	2	40.00%
胃肠炎型 Gastroenteritis	1141	3003	2	0.07%
暗顶蘑菇 <i>Agaricus atrodiscus</i>	1	6	0	0
布莱萨蘑菇和草地马勃(食用) <i>Agaricus bresadolanus</i> & <i>Lycoperdon pratense</i> E	1	2	0	0
黄斑蘑菇 <i>Agaricus xanthodermus</i>	2	3	0	0
除赭鳞蘑菇(食用)和林地蘑菇近似种(食用)外的多个蘑菇属未定种 (Li et al. (2020) 报道) <i>Agaricus</i> spp. except <i>A. subrufescens</i> E & <i>A. aff. arvensis</i> E (reported in Li et al. (2020))	4	10	0	0
一个蘑菇属未定种 <i>Agaricus</i> sp.	1	2	0	0
奇丝地花菌 <i>Albatrellus dispansus</i>	1	1	0	0
大果薄瓢牛肝菌 <i>Baorangia major</i>	6	23	0	0
大果薄瓢牛肝菌和假美柄薄瓢牛肝菌 <i>Baorangia major</i> & <i>B. pseudocalopus</i>	1	7	0	0

... 待续 continued below

▼ 表 6. (续表)
Table 6. (continued)

误食类型 Ingestion types	事件数 Incidents	中毒人数 Patients	死亡人数 Deaths	死亡率 Fatality
假美柄薄瓢牛肝菌 <i>Baorangia pseudocalopus</i>	4	10	0	0
一个薄瓢牛肝菌属未定种 <i>Baorangia</i> sp.	1	5	0	0
木生条孢牛肝菌近似种 <i>Boletellus</i> aff. <i>emodensis</i>	1	1	0	0
隐纹条孢牛肝菌 <i>Boletellus indistinctus</i>	1	6	0	0
德氏青褶伞和橙黄硬皮马勃 <i>Chlorophyllum demangei</i> & <i>Scleroderma aurantiacum</i>	1	2	0	0
球盖青褶伞 <i>Chlorophyllum globosum</i>	14	50	0	0
球盖青褶伞近似种 <i>Chlorophyllum</i> aff. <i>globosum</i>	7	25	0	0
变红青褶伞 <i>Chlorophyllum hortense</i>	11	24	0	0
变红青褶伞和一个杯伞属未定种(神经) <i>Chlorophyllum hortense</i> & <i>Clitocybe</i> sp. P	1	1	0	0
大青褶伞 <i>Chlorophyllum molybdites</i>	534	1107	0	0
大青褶伞和变红青褶伞 <i>Chlorophyllum molybdites</i> & <i>C. hortense</i>	2	8	0	0
大青褶伞和近江粉褶蕈 <i>Chlorophyllum molybdites</i> & <i>Entoloma omiense</i>	1	1	0	0
大青褶伞和毛头鬼伞(食用、胃肠) <i>Chlorophyllum molybdites</i> & <i>Coprinus comatus</i> E, G	1	1	0	0
大青褶伞和古尼掘氏霉(药用) <i>Chlorophyllum molybdites</i> & <i>Drechmeria gunnii</i> M	1	3	0	0
大青褶伞近似种 <i>Chlorophyllum</i> aff. <i>molybdites</i>	1	1	0	0
多个青褶伞属未定种 <i>Chlorophyllum</i> spp.	3	9	0	0
无味拟金钱菌、大孢斑褶菇(神经)、一个蘑菇属未定种(未定)、白网球菌(未定)和中华白环蘑(未定) <i>Collybiopsis indocta</i> , <i>Panaeolus papilionaceus</i> P, <i>Agaricus</i> sp. U, <i>Ileodictyon gracile</i> U & <i>Leucoagaricus sinicus</i> U	1	4	0	0
晶粒小鬼伞 <i>Coprinellus micaceus</i>	1	1	0	0
晶粒小鬼伞和双孢斑褶菇(神经) <i>Coprinellus micaceus</i> & <i>Panaeolus bisporus</i> P	1	3	0	0
艾地拟鬼伞 <i>Coprinopsis aesontiensis</i>	1	6	0	0
墨汁拟鬼伞 <i>Coprinopsis atramentaria</i>	3	4	0	0
斯氏拟鬼伞 <i>Coprinopsis strossmayeri</i>	1	2	0	0
毛头鬼伞 <i>Coprinus comatus</i>	1	1	0	0

... 待续 continued below

▼ 表 6. (续表)
Table 6. (continued)

误食类型 Ingestion types	事件数 Incidents	中毒人数 Patients	死亡人数 Deaths	死亡率 Fatality
丛生粉褶蕈 <i>Entoloma caespitosum</i>	3	7	0	0
近江粉褶蕈 <i>Entoloma omiense</i>	68	199	0	0
近江粉褶蕈和黄白乳牛肝菌(食用、胃肠) <i>Entoloma omiense</i> & <i>Suillus placidus</i> E, G	1	4	0	0
近江粉褶蕈、杵柄鹅膏(神精)、褐环乳牛肝菌(食用、胃肠)、松林乳牛肝菌(食用、胃肠)、网纹马勃复合群(食用、药用)和鲜艳乳菇(食用) <i>Entoloma omiense</i> , <i>Amanita sinocitrina</i> P, <i>Suillus luteus</i> E, G, <i>S. pinetorum</i> E, G, <i>Lycoperdon perlatum</i> complex E, M & <i>Lactarius vividus</i> E	1	5	0	0
近江粉褶蕈和杵柄鹅膏(神精) <i>Entoloma omiense</i> & <i>Amanita sinocitrina</i> P	1	7	0	0
近江粉褶蕈、黄盖堪多脆柄菇(神精)和一个粉褶蕈属未定种(未定) <i>Entoloma omiense</i> , <i>Candolleomyces candolleanus</i> P & <i>Entoloma</i> sp. U	1	1	0	0
近江粉褶蕈和一个粉褶蕈属未定种(未定) <i>Entoloma omiense</i> & <i>Entoloma</i> sp. U	1	2	0	0
近江粉褶蕈和一个裸伞属未定种(未定) <i>Entoloma omiense</i> & <i>Gymnopus</i> sp. U	1	6	0	0
近江粉褶蕈和一个小蘑菇属未定种(未定) <i>Entoloma omiense</i> & <i>Micropsalliota</i> sp. U	1	3	0	0
近江粉褶蕈和绿桂红菇(食用) <i>Entoloma omiense</i> & <i>Russula viridicinnamomea</i> E	1	2	0	0
近江粉褶蕈、红盖白鬼伞(未定)和大盖小皮伞 <i>Entoloma omiense</i> , <i>Leucocoprinus rubrotinctus</i> U & <i>Marasmius maximus</i> E	1	10	0	0
近江粉褶蕈、一个粉褶蕈属未定种(未定)、头状秃马勃(食用、药用)和鲜艳乳菇(食用) <i>Entoloma omiense</i> , <i>Entoloma</i> sp. U, <i>Calvatia craniiformis</i> E, M & <i>Lactarius vividus</i> E	1	4	0	0
近江粉褶蕈、白豆马勃复合群(食用、药用)、褐网柄牛肝菌(食用)和鲜艳乳菇(食用) <i>Entoloma omiense</i> , <i>Pisolithus albus</i> complex E, M, <i>Retiboletus fuscus</i> E & <i>Lactarius vividus</i> E	1	2	0	0
近江粉褶蕈、一个鹅膏属未定种(未定)、宽褶黑乳菇近似种(食用)、壳状红菇(食用)和绿桂乳菇(食用) <i>Entoloma omiense</i> , <i>Amanita</i> sp. U, <i>Lactarius</i> aff. <i>gerardii</i> E, <i>Russula crustosa</i> E & <i>R. viridicinnamomea</i> E	1	6	0	0
近江粉褶蕈和中华鹅膏(食用) <i>Entoloma omiense</i> & <i>Amanita sinensis</i> E	1	7	0	0
方孢粉褶蕈 <i>Entoloma quadratum</i>	1	2	0	0
褐盖粉褶蕈近似种 <i>Entoloma</i> aff. <i>rhodopolium</i>	1	5	0	0
毒粉褶蕈近似种 <i>Entoloma</i> aff. <i>sinuatum</i>	5	20	0	0

... 待续 continued below

▼ 表 6. (续表)
Table 6. (continued)

误食类型 Ingestion types	事件数 Incidents	中毒人数 Patients	死亡人数 Deaths	死亡率 Fatality
直柄粉褶蕈 <i>Entoloma strictius</i>	1	2	0	0
直柄粉褶蕈近似种 <i>Entoloma aff. strictius</i>	1	3	0	0
近毒粉褶蕈近似种 <i>Entoloma aff. subsinuatum</i>	1	4	0	0
近毒粉褶蕈近似种和栎圆头伞(食用) <i>Entoloma aff. subsinuatum</i> & <i>Descolea quercina</i> E	1	9	0	0
一个粉褶蕈属未定种 <i>Entoloma sp.</i>	1	3	0	0
一个粉褶蕈属未定种、假羚色红菇近似种(未定)和细绒盖牛肝菌(食用) <i>Entoloma sp.</i> , <i>Russula aff. pseudobubalina</i> U & <i>Xerocomus parvulus</i> E	1	2	0	0
多个粉褶蕈属未定种 <i>Entoloma spp.</i>	17	51	0	0
中华格氏蘑 <i>Gerhardtia sinensis</i>	6	19	0	0
密褶裸脚伞 <i>Gymnopus densilamellatus</i>	5	23	0	0
密褶裸脚伞、栎裸脚伞和毡绒毛缘菇(未定) <i>Gymnopus densilamellatus</i> , <i>G. dryophilus</i> & <i>Ripartites tricholoma</i> U	1	2	0	0
密褶裸脚伞近似种 <i>Gymnopus aff. densilamellatus</i>	2	5	0	0
栎裸脚伞 <i>Gymnopus dryophilus</i>	2	3	0	0
栎裸脚伞、密褶裸脚伞、松林乳牛肝菌(食用、胃肠)、红蜡蘑(食用)、碱紫漏斗伞(食用)、紫柄红菇(食用)、蜡味红菇(未定)和一个裸脚伞属未定种(未定) <i>Gymnopus dryophilus</i> , <i>G. densilamellatus</i> , <i>Suillus pinetorum</i> E, <i>G. Laccaria laccata</i> E, <i>Infundibulicybe alkaliviolascens</i> E, <i>Russula violeipes</i> E, <i>R. cerolens</i> U & <i>Gymnopus sp.</i> U	1	3	0	0
臭裸脚伞 <i>Gymnopus dysodes</i>	1	3	0	0
相似裸脚伞 <i>Gymnopus similis</i>	2	3	0	0
一个裸脚伞属未定种和一个蘑菇属未定种(未定) <i>Gymnopus sp.</i> & <i>Agaricus sp.</i> U	1	2	0	0
一个裸脚伞属未定种和一个红菇属未定种(未定) <i>Gymnopus sp.</i> & <i>Russula sp.</i> U	1	2	0	0
长柄网孢牛肝菌 <i>Heimioporus gaojiaocong</i>	4	10	0	0
日本网孢牛肝菌 <i>Heimioporus japonicus</i>	3	11	0	0
裂盖湿伞 <i>Hygrocybe rimosa</i>	1	2	0	0
簇生垂幕菇 <i>Hypholoma fasciculare</i>	3	9	0	0

... 待续 continued below

▼ 表 6. (续表)
Table 6. (continued)

误食类型 Ingestion types	事件数 Incidents	中毒人数 Patients	死亡人数 Deaths	死亡率 Fatality
暗棕乳菇 <i>Lactarius atrobrunneus</i>	1	1	0	0
毛脚乳菇 <i>Lactarius hirtipes</i>	1	2	0	0
蜡蘑状乳菇 <i>Lactarius laccarioides</i>	2	11	0	0
紫色乳菇 <i>Lactarius purpureus</i>	1	1	0	0
红棕乳菇 <i>Lactarius rubrobrunneus</i>	1	1	0	0
红皱乳菇 <i>Lactarius rubrocorrugatus</i>	3	8	0	0
近大西洋乳菇或近毛脚乳菇 <i>Lactarius subatlanticus</i> or <i>L. subhirtipes</i>	1	1	0	0
近毛脚乳菇 <i>Lactarius subhirtipes</i>	3	9	0	0
毛头乳菇和杯伞状大金钱菌 <i>Lactarius torminosus</i> & <i>Megacollybia clitocyboidea</i>	1	4	0	0
迷惑多汁乳菇、长绒多汁乳菇、辣味多汁乳菇近似种 和柔毛多汁乳菇 <i>Lactifluus deceptivus</i> , <i>L. pilosus</i> , <i>L. aff. piperatus</i> & <i>L. puberulus</i>	1	2	0	0
变绿多汁乳菇 <i>Lactifluus aff. glaucescens</i>	1	3	0	0
辣味多汁乳菇(食用、胃肠) <i>Lactifluus piperatus</i> E, G	1	5	0	0
假黄柄多汁乳菇 <i>Lactifluus pseudoluteopus</i>	3	9	0	0
绒白多汁乳菇 <i>Lactifluus vellereus</i>	1	7	0	0
一个兰茂牛肝菌属未定种 <i>Lanmaoa</i> sp.	1	2	0	0
石灰白鬼伞 <i>Leucocoprinus cretaceus</i>	1	1	0	0
石灰白鬼伞和粗柄白鬼伞 <i>Leucocoprinus cretaceus</i> & <i>L. cepistipes</i>	1	2	0	0
纯白鬼伞 <i>Leucocoprinus leucothites</i>	2	6	0	0
丁香紫白鬼伞复合群 <i>Leucocoprinus purpureoilacinus</i> complex	1	1	0	0
灰棕钨囊蘑 <i>Melanoleuca griseobrunnea</i>	1	2	0	0
矮钨囊蘑 <i>Melanoleuca humilis</i>	1	2	0	0
糠鳞小蘑菇 <i>Micropsalliota furfuracea</i>	1	2	0	0
南比新假革耳近似种 <i>Neonothopanus aff. nambi</i>	2	4	0	0

... 待续 continued below

▼ 表 6. (续表)
Table 6. (continued)

误食类型 Ingestion types	事件数 Incidents	中毒人数 Patients	死亡人数 Deaths	死亡率 Fatality
棕褶类脐菇 <i>Omphalotus guepiniformis</i>	12	57	0	0
棕褶类脐菇和高大环柄菇(食用、药用、胃肠) <i>Omphalotus guepiniformis</i> & <i>Macrolepiota procea</i> E, M, G	1	8	0	0
发光类脐菇 <i>Omphalotus olearius</i>	5	23	0	0
云南类脐菇 <i>Omphalotus yunnanensis</i>	3	10	0	0
一个类脐菇属未定种 <i>Omphalotus</i> sp.	4	44	0	0
黏皮鳞伞 <i>Pholiota lubrica</i>	1	3	0	0
多环鳞伞 <i>Pholiota multicingulata</i>	3	13	0	0
近红粉末牛肝菌、斑柄红菇、绿盖裘氏牛肝菌和松林乳牛肝菌(食用、胃肠) <i>Pulveroboletus subrufus</i> , <i>Russula punctipes</i> , <i>Chiuia virens</i> & <i>Suillus pinetorum</i> E, G	1	2	0	0
近红粉末牛肝菌、假黄柄多汁乳菇近似种、近粉霜多汁乳菇(食用)、多汁乳菇(食用)、巨大侧耳(食用)和壳状红菇(食用) <i>Pulveroboletus subrufus</i> , <i>Lactifluus</i> aff. <i>pseudoluteopus</i> U, <i>L. subpruinus</i> E, <i>L. volemus</i> E, <i>Pleurotus giganteus</i> E & <i>Russula crustosa</i> E	1	1	0	0
纤细枝瑚菌 <i>Ramaria gracilis</i>	1	1	0	0
宽孢红孔牛肝菌 <i>Rubroboletus latisporus</i>	2	10	0	0
中华红孔牛肝菌 <i>Rubroboletus sinicus</i>	1	2	0	0
中华红孔牛肝菌和密鳞新牛肝菌近似种(未定) <i>Rubroboletus sinicus</i> & <i>Neoboletus</i> aff. <i>multipunctatus</i> U	1	4	0	0
中华红孔牛肝菌和褐网柄牛肝菌(食用) <i>Rubroboletus sinicus</i> & <i>Retiboletus fuscus</i> E	2	23	0	0
短孢红菇 <i>Russula brevispora</i>	1	1	0	0
短孢红菇、臭黄红菇、斑柄红菇、假褐云斑鹅膏(肾衰)、红褶多汁乳菇(未定)、凋萎状多汁乳菇(未定)、金绿红菇(未定)、复囊多汁乳菇近似种(食用)、华热带多汁乳菇近似种(食用)、翘鳞韧伞(食用)、鳞盖红菇(食用)和菱红菇(食用) <i>Russula brevispora</i> , <i>R. foetens</i> , <i>R. punctipes</i> , <i>Amanita pseudoporphyria</i> AKF, <i>Lactifluus roseophyllus</i> U, <i>L. vitellinus</i> U, <i>Russula aureoviridis</i> U, <i>Lactifluus</i> aff. <i>ambicystidiatus</i> E, <i>L. aff. tropicosinicus</i> E, <i>Lentinus squarrosulus</i> E, <i>Russula lepida</i> E & <i>R. vesca</i> E	1	2	0	0

... 待续 continued below

▼ 表 6. (续表)
Table 6. (continued)

误食类型 Ingestion types	事件数 Incidents	中毒人数 Patients	死亡人数 Deaths	死亡率 Fatality
短孢红菇、斑柄红菇、红基红菇、新苦粉孢牛肝菌、 隐纹条孢牛肝菌、暗缘乳菇、假褐云斑鹅膏(肾衰)、格纹 鹅膏(神经)、长囊体圆孔牛肝菌(未定)、金绿红菇(未定)、紫 疣红菇(未定)、松林乳牛肝菌(食用、胃肠)、壳状红菇(食用)、 一个蚁巢伞属未定种(食用)、近粉霜多汁乳菇(食用)、巨大 侧耳(食用)、致密红菇(食用)、假巴卢粉孢牛肝菌(食用)和亚 绒盖牛肝菌(食用) <i>Russula brevispora</i> , <i>R. punctipes</i> , <i>R. rufobasalis</i> , <i>Tylophilus neofelleus</i> , <i>Boletellus indistinctus</i> , <i>Lactarius atromarginatus</i> , <i>Amanita</i> <i>pseudoporphyria</i> AKF, <i>A. fritillaria</i> P, <i>Gyroporus longicystidiatus</i> U, <i>Russula aureoviridis</i> U, <i>R. purpureoverrucosa</i> U, <i>Suillus pinetorum</i> E, G, <i>Russula crustosa</i> E, <i>Termitomyces</i> sp. E, <i>Lactifluus subpruinus</i> E, <i>Pleurotus giganteus</i> E, <i>Russula compacta</i> E, <i>Tylophilus pseudoballoui</i> E & <i>Xerocomus subtomentosus</i> E	1	2	0	0
毒红菇近似种 <i>Russula</i> aff. <i>emetica</i>	1	3	0	0
变黄红菇 <i>Russula flavescens</i>	1	3	0	0
变黄红菇和相似鹅膏近似种(未定) <i>Russula flavescens</i> & <i>Amanita</i> aff. <i>similis</i> U	1	1	0	0
臭黄红菇 <i>Russula foetens</i>	4	9	0	0
可爱红菇 <i>Russula grata</i>	1	2	0	0
可爱红菇、近臭黄红菇近似种、变绿多汁乳菇近似种、 香红菇(未定)、假怡人色红菇(未定)、萨氏红菇(未定)、波状 粉褶蕈近似种(未定)、蓝黄红菇(食用)、菱红菇(食用)和变绿 红菇(食用) <i>Russula grata</i> , <i>R. aff. subfoetens</i> , <i>Lactifluus</i> aff. <i>gaucescens</i> , <i>Russula</i> <i>fragrantissima</i> U, <i>R. pseudoamoenicolor</i> U, <i>R. sarnarii</i> U, <i>Entoloma</i> aff. <i>undatum</i> U, <i>Russula cyanoxantha</i> E, <i>R. vesca</i> E & <i>R. virescens</i> E	1	3	0	0
脏红菇和角孢粉褶蕈近似种 <i>Russula illota</i> & <i>Entoloma</i> aff. <i>abortivum</i>	1	2	0	0
日本红菇 <i>Russula japonica</i>	20	49	0	0
日本红菇复合群 <i>Russula japonica</i> complex	150	425	0	0
日本红菇复合群和暗盖淡鳞鹅膏 <i>Russula japonica</i> complex & <i>Amanita sepiacea</i>	1	3	0	0
日本红菇复合群和近江粉褶蕈 <i>Russula japonica</i> complex & <i>Entoloma omiense</i>	1	1	0	0
日本红菇复合群和臭黄红菇 <i>Russula japonica</i> complex & <i>R. foetens</i>	4	8	0	0
日本红菇复合群和斑柄红菇 <i>Russula japonica</i> complex & <i>R. punctipes</i>	3	7	0	0
日本红菇复合群、近江粉褶蕈和一个蘑菇属未定种(未定) <i>Russula japonica</i> complex, <i>Entoloma omiense</i> & <i>Agaricus</i> sp. U	1	3	0	0
日本红菇复合群、斑柄红菇、变绿红菇(食用)和狮黄多汁 乳菇(食用) <i>Russula japonica</i> complex, <i>R. punctipes</i> , <i>R. virescens</i> E & <i>Lactifluus</i> <i>leoninus</i> E	1	3	0	0

... 待续 continued below

▼ 表 6. (续表)
Table 6. (continued)

误食类型 Ingestion types	事件数 Incidents	中毒人数 Patients	死亡人数 Deaths	死亡率 Fatality
日本红菇复合群、格纹鹅膏(神经)和壳状红菇(食用) <i>Russula japonica</i> complex, <i>Amanita fritillaria</i> P & <i>Russula crustosa</i> E, M	1	1	0	0
日本红菇复合群和一个钉菇属未定种(未定) <i>Russula japonica</i> complex & <i>Gomphus</i> sp. U	1	1	0	0
日本红菇复合群和一个红菇属未定种(未定) <i>Russula japonica</i> complex & <i>Russula</i> sp. U	1	2	0	0
日本红菇复合群、一个湿伞属未定种(未定)和多汁乳菇(食用) <i>Russula japonica</i> complex, <i>Hygrocybe</i> sp. U & <i>Lactifluus volemus</i> E	1	5	0	0
日本红菇复合群、润滑锤舌菌(神经)、蜡味红菇(未定)和异孢褶孔牛肝菌(食用) <i>Russula japonica</i> complex, <i>Leotia lubrica</i> P, <i>Russula cerolens</i> E & <i>Phylloporus dimorphus</i> E	1	2	0	0
日本红菇复合群和铜绿红菇(食用) <i>Russula japonica</i> complex & <i>R. aeruginea</i> E	1	2	0	0
日本红菇复合群和致密红菇(食用) <i>Russula japonica</i> complex & <i>R. compacta</i> E	1	4	0	0
日本红菇复合群、点柄乳牛肝菌(食用、胃肠)和假巴卢粉孢牛肝菌(食用) <i>Russula japonica</i> complex, <i>Suillus granulatus</i> E, G & <i>Tylopilus pseudoballoui</i> E	1	1	0	0
日本红菇复合群和血红菇(食用) <i>Russula japonica</i> complex & <i>R. sanguinea</i> E	1	3	0	0
日本红菇近似种 <i>Russula</i> aff. <i>japonica</i>	10	43	0	0
假日本红菇 <i>Russula pseudojaponica</i>	11	45	0	0
假日本红菇、臭黄红菇、斑柄红菇、长绒多汁乳菇、点柄乳牛肝菌(食用、胃肠)和变绿红菇(食用) <i>Russula pseudojaponica</i> , <i>R. foetens</i> , <i>R. punctipes</i> , <i>Lactifluus pilosus</i> , <i>Suillus granulatus</i> E, G & <i>Russula virescens</i> E	1	5	0	0
假日本红菇、斑柄红菇、多个红菇属未定种(未定)和绿桂红菇(食用) <i>Russula pseudojaponica</i> , <i>R. punctipes</i> , <i>Russula</i> spp. U & <i>R. viridicinnamomea</i> E	1	2	0	0
假日本红菇、一个红菇属未定种(未定)和一个鹅膏属未定种(未定) <i>Russula pseudojaponica</i> , <i>Russula</i> sp. U & <i>Amanita</i> sp. U	1	2	0	0
假日本红菇、一个红菇属未定种(未定)和高大鹅膏近似种(食用) <i>Russula pseudojaponica</i> , <i>Russula</i> sp. U & <i>Amanita</i> aff. <i>princeps</i> E	1	1	0	0
假日本红菇、青褶缘红菇(未定)、一个红菇属未定种(未定)和密褶红菇(食用) <i>Russula pseudojaponica</i> , <i>R. callainomarginis</i> U, <i>Russula</i> sp. U & <i>R. densifolia</i> E	1	6	0	0
假日本红菇、密褶红菇(食用)和头状秃马勃(食用、药用) <i>Russula pseudojaponica</i> , <i>R. densifolia</i> E & <i>Calvatia craniiformis</i> E, M	1	4	0	0
斑柄红菇 <i>Russula punctipes</i>	1	6	0	0

... 待续 continued below

▼ 表 6. (续表)
Table 6. (continued)

误食类型 Ingestion types	事件数 Incidents	中毒人数 Patients	死亡人数 Deaths	死亡率 Fatality
斑柄红菇、青褶缘红菇(未定)、一个红菇属未定种(未定)、 灰褶鹅膏(未定)和格纹鹅膏(神经) <i>Russula punctipes</i> , <i>R. callainomarginis</i> U, <i>Russula</i> sp. U, <i>Amanita</i> <i>griseofolia</i> U & <i>A. fritillaria</i> P	1	2	0	0
红基红菇 <i>Russula rufobasalis</i>	2	4	0	0
红基红菇、暗缘乳菇、格纹鹅膏(神经)和蜜黄红菇(食用) <i>Russula rufobasalis</i> , <i>Lactarius atromarginatus</i> , <i>Amanita fritillaria</i> P & <i>Russula ochroleuca</i> E	1	2	0	0
红基红菇、格纹鹅膏(神经)、香红菇近似种(未定)、紫萨氏 丝膜菌(未定)、致密红菇(食用)、烟色红菇(食用)和近黑紫红 菇(食用) <i>Russula rufobasalis</i> , <i>Amanita fritillaria</i> P, <i>Russula</i> aff. <i>fragrantissima</i> U, <i>Thaxterogaster purpurascens</i> U, <i>Russula compacta</i> E, <i>R. nigricans</i> E & <i>R. subatropurpurea</i> E	1	2	0	0
一个红菇属未定种 <i>Russula</i> sp.	1	4	0	0
网隙硬皮马勃 <i>Scleroderma areolatum</i>	1	12	0	0
白硬皮马勃近似种 <i>Scleroderma</i> aff. <i>albidum</i>	3	11	0	0
网隙硬皮马勃近似种和云南硬皮马勃(食用) <i>Scleroderma</i> aff. <i>areolatum</i> & <i>S. yunnanense</i> E	1	9	2	22.22%
光硬皮马勃 <i>Scleroderma cepa</i>	24	82	0	0
光硬皮马勃和马勃状硬皮马勃(食用、药用) <i>Scleroderma cepa</i> & <i>S. bovista</i> E, M	1	2	0	0
橙黄硬皮马勃 <i>Scleroderma citrinum</i>	1	1	0	0
毒硬皮马勃 <i>Scleroderma venenatum</i>	1	2	0	0
一个硬皮马勃属未定种 <i>Scleroderma</i> sp.	1	1	0	0
一个硬皮马勃属未定种、暗顶蘑菇、小毒蝇鹅膏(神经) 和一个卢氏菇属未定种(未定) <i>Scleroderma</i> sp., <i>Agaricus atrodiscus</i> , <i>Amanita melleiceps</i> P & <i>Lulesia</i> sp. U	1	3	0	0
点柄乳牛肝菌(食用、胃肠) <i>Suillus granulatus</i> E, G	3	5	0	0
点柄乳牛肝菌(食用、胃肠)、杵柄鹅膏(神经)、灰褶鹅膏(未定)、 多个红菇属未定种(未定)、一个马勃属未定种(未定)和一个 裸脚伞属未定种(未定) <i>Suillus granulatus</i> E, G, <i>Amanita sinocitrina</i> P, <i>A. griseofolia</i> U, <i>Russula</i> spp. U, <i>Lycoperdon</i> sp. U & <i>Gymnopus</i> sp. U	1	1	0	0
点柄乳牛肝菌(食用、胃肠)和红汁乳菇(食用) <i>Suillus granulatus</i> E, G & <i>Lactarius hatsudake</i> E	1	1	0	0

... 待续 continued below

▼ 表 6. (续表)
Table 6. (continued)

误食类型 Ingestion types	事件数 Incidents	中毒人数 Patients	死亡人数 Deaths	死亡率 Fatality
华虎皮乳牛肝菌(食用、胃肠)、灰托鹅膏复合群(未定)、鹿色蜜环丝膜菌(未定)、拟栗色垂边红孢牛肝菌(未定)、波状粉褶蕈(未定)、短囊体乳菇(未定)、多个红菇属未定种(未定)、肉桂色乳菇(食用)和致密红菇(食用) <i>Suillus phylopiectus</i> E, G, <i>Amanita vaginata</i> complex U, <i>Cortinarius hinnuleoarmillatus</i> U, <i>Veloporphyrellus pseudovelatus</i> U, <i>Entoloma undatum</i> U, <i>Lactarius brachycystidiatus</i> U, <i>Russula</i> spp. U, <i>Lactarius cinnamomeus</i> E & <i>Russula compacta</i> E	1	2	0	0
虎皮乳牛肝菌近似种(食用、胃肠) <i>Suillus</i> aff. <i>spraguei</i> E, G	1	5	0	0
松林乳牛肝菌(食用、胃肠) <i>Suillus pinetorum</i> E, G	1	8	0	0
松林乳牛肝菌(食用、胃肠)、爪哇鹅膏(食用)、白牛肝菌(食用)和暗褐脉柄牛肝菌(食用) <i>Suillus pinetorum</i> E, G, <i>Amanita javanica</i> E, <i>Boletus bainiugan</i> E & <i>Phlebopus portentosus</i> E	1	8	0	0
有毒异色牛肝菌 <i>Sutorius venenatus</i>	11	34	0	0
有毒异色牛肝菌和马勃状硬皮马勃(食用、药用) <i>Sutorius venenatus</i> & <i>Scleroderma bovista</i> E, M	1	2	0	0
有毒异色牛肝菌和彝食黄肉牛肝菌(食用) <i>Sutorius venenatus</i> & <i>Butyriboletus yicibus</i> E	1	2	0	0
一个异色牛肝菌属未定种 <i>Sutorius</i> sp.	1	3	0	0
高地口蘑 <i>Tricholoma highlandense</i>	2	3	0	0
高地口蘑和一个口蘑属未定种 <i>Tricholoma highlandense</i> & <i>Tricholoma</i> sp.	1	6	0	0
高地口蘑、丛毛疣钉菇复合群、一个牛肝菌属未定种(未定)、多个红菇属未定种(未定)和一个枝瑚菌属未定种(未定) <i>Tricholoma highlandense</i> , <i>Turbinellus floccosus</i> complex, <i>Boletus</i> sp. U, <i>Russula</i> spp. U & <i>Ramaria</i> sp. U	1	4	0	0
橄榄色口蘑 <i>Tricholoma olivaceum</i>	2	4	0	0
橄榄色口蘑、近毒粉褶蕈近似种和一个鹅膏属未定种(未定) <i>Tricholoma olivaceum</i> , <i>Entoloma</i> aff. <i>subsiniatum</i> & <i>Amanita</i> sp. U	1	1	0	0
中华豹斑口蘑 <i>Tricholoma sinopardinum</i>	1	2	0	0
中华豹斑口蘑、中华灰褐纹口蘑(食用)、粗质乳菇(食用)和一个蘑菇属未定种(未定) <i>Tricholoma sinopardinum</i> , <i>T. sinoportentosum</i> E, <i>Lactarius deterrimus</i> E & <i>Agaricus</i> sp. U	1	3	0	0
直立口蘑 <i>Tricholoma stans</i>	3	12	0	0
直立口蘑、一个蜡伞属未定种(未定)和云南蜡伞(食用) <i>Tricholoma stans</i> , <i>Hygrophorus</i> sp. U & <i>Hygrophorus yunnanensis</i> E	1	6	0	0
直立口蘑近似种 <i>Tricholoma</i> aff. <i>stans</i>	2	5	0	0

... 待续 continued below

▼ 表 6. (续表)
Table 6. (continued)

误食类型 Ingestion types	事件数 Incidents	中毒人数 Patients	死亡人数 Deaths	死亡率 Fatality
赭红拟口蘑复合群、象头山美柄牛肝菌(未定)、一个魔王牛肝菌属未定种(未定)、一个绒盖牛肝菌属未定种(未定)、兰茂牛肝菌(食用、神精)和白牛肝菌(食用) <i>Tricholomopsis rutilans</i> complex, <i>Caloboletus xiangtoushanensis</i> U, <i>Imperator</i> sp. U, <i>Xerocomus</i> sp. U, <i>Lanmaoa asiatica</i> E, P & <i>Boletus bainiugan</i> E	1	2	0	0
苦粉孢牛肝菌、点柄乳牛肝菌(食用、胃肠)、格纹鹅膏(神精)、红黄鹅膏近似种(食用)、高大鹅膏(食用)、蜡味红菇(未定)、一个红菇属未定种(未定)、一个多汁乳菇属未定种(未定)和一个丝膜菌属未定种(未定) <i>Tylopilus felleus</i> , <i>Suillus granulatus</i> E, G, <i>Amanita fritillaria</i> P, A. aff. <i>hemibapha</i> E, A. <i>princeps</i> E, <i>Russula cerolens</i> U, <i>Russula</i> sp. U, <i>Lactifluus</i> sp. U & <i>Cortinarius</i> sp. U	1	2	0	0
新苦粉孢牛肝菌 <i>Tylopilus neofelleus</i>	2	2	0	0
新苦粉孢牛肝菌、窄孢兰茂牛肝菌(未定)、密鳞新牛肝菌(未定)、达瓦里多汁乳菇(未定)、辣味多汁乳菇(食用、胃肠)、网纹牛肝菌(食用)、假巴卢粉孢牛肝菌(食用)、暗褐新牛肝菌(食用)、中华网柄牛肝菌(食用)和皱盖牛肝菌(食用) <i>Tylopilus vinosobrunneus</i> , <i>Lanmaoa angustispora</i> U, <i>Neoboletus multipunctatus</i> U, <i>Lactifluus dwaliensis</i> U, L. <i>piperatus</i> E, G, <i>Boletus reticulatus</i> E, <i>Tylopilus pseudoballoui</i> E, <i>Neoboletus obscureumbrinus</i> E, <i>Retiboletus sinensis</i> E & <i>Rugiboletus exterioirentalis</i> E	1	2	0	0
神经精神型 Psycho-neurological Disorder	283	844	1	0.12%
环鳞鹅膏 <i>Amanita concentrica</i>	6	9	0	0
环足鹅膏和血红菇(食用) <i>Amanita collariata</i> & <i>Russula sanguinea</i> E	1	4	0	0
格纹鹅膏 <i>Amanita fritillaria</i>	2	8	0	0
灰豹斑鹅膏和臭黄红菇 <i>Amanita griseopantherina</i> & <i>Russula foetens</i>	1	12	0	0
假球基鹅膏 <i>Amanita ibotengutake</i>	1	17	0	0
黄顶白缘鹅膏 <i>Amanita melleialba</i>	1	1	0	0
小毒蝇鹅膏 <i>Amanita melleiceps</i>	8	27	0	0
小毒蝇鹅膏和一个裸脚伞属未定种(未定) <i>Amanita melleiceps</i> & <i>Gymnopus</i> sp. U	1	2	0	0
东方黄盖鹅膏 <i>Amanita orientigemmata</i>	2	3	0	0
红褐鹅膏和一个鹅膏属未定种(未定) <i>Amanita orsonii</i> & <i>Amanita</i> sp. U	1	3	0	0
红褐鹅膏、假灰托鹅膏(未定)和乌黑粉褶蕈近似种(未定) <i>Amanita orsonii</i> , A. <i>pseudovaginata</i> U & <i>Entoloma</i> aff. <i>subcorvinum</i> U	1	2	0	0
小豹斑鹅膏 <i>Amanita parvipantherina</i>	3	11	0	0

... 待续 continued below

▼ 表 6. (续表)
Table 6. (continued)

误食类型 Ingestion types	事件数 Incidents	中毒人数 Patients	死亡人数 Deaths	死亡率 Fatality
假豹斑鹅膏 <i>Amanita pseudopantherina</i>	1	1	0	0
假残托鹅膏 <i>Amanita pseudosychnopyraxis</i>	4	16	0	0
假残托鹅膏近似种和土红鹅膏 <i>Amanita aff. pseudosychnopyraxis</i> & <i>A. rufoferruginea</i>	1	5	0	0
土红鹅膏 <i>Amanita rufoferruginea</i>	17	49	1	2.04%
土红鹅膏和球基鹅膏 <i>Amanita rufoferruginea</i> & <i>A. subglobosa</i>	1	3	0	0
土红鹅膏、致密红菇(食用)和一个蚁巢伞属未定种(食用) <i>Amanita rufoferruginea</i> , <i>Russula compacta</i> E & <i>Termitomyces</i> sp. E	1	4	0	0
暹罗鹅膏 <i>Amanita siamensis</i>	1	2	0	0
暹罗鹅膏和一个蚁巢伞属未定种(食用) <i>Amanita siamensis</i> & <i>Termitomyces</i> sp. E	1	3	0	0
黄鳞鹅膏近似种 <i>Amanita aff. subfrostiana</i>	1	2	0	0
球基鹅膏 <i>Amanita subglobosa</i>	33	109	0	0
球基鹅膏、假褐云斑鹅膏(肾衰)和彩色豆马勃复合群(食用、药用) <i>Amanita subglobosa</i> , <i>A. pseudoporphyria</i> AKF & <i>Pisolithus arhizus</i> complex E, M	1	4	0	0
球基鹅膏和暗顶蘑菇(胃肠) <i>Amanita subglobosa</i> & <i>Agaricus atrodiscus</i> G	1	3	0	0
球基鹅膏近似种 <i>Amanita aff. subglobosa</i>	1	2	0	0
残托鹅膏有环变型 <i>Amanita sychnopyraxis</i> f. <i>subannulata</i>	18	86	0	0
残托鹅膏有环变型、假褐云斑鹅膏(肾衰)和栗色鹅膏(未定) <i>Amanita sychnopyraxis</i> f. <i>subannulata</i> , <i>A. pseudoporphyria</i> AKF & <i>A. castanea</i> U	1	5	0	0
残托鹅膏有环变型和大青褶伞(胃肠) <i>Amanita sychnopyraxis</i> f. <i>subannulata</i> & <i>Chlorophyllum molybdites</i> G	1	1	0	0
锥鳞白鹅膏近似种 <i>Amanita aff. virgineoides</i>	1	1	0	0
煤烟色变黑牛肝菌 <i>Anthracoportus holophaeus</i>	1	1	0	0
煤烟色变黑牛肝菌和近毛脚乳菇 <i>Anthracoportus holophaeus</i> & <i>Lactarius subhirtipes</i>	1	3	0	0
煤烟色变黑牛肝菌近似种 <i>Anthracoportus aff. holophaeus</i>	1	2	0	0
黑紫变黑牛肝菌 <i>Anthracoportus nigropurpureus</i>	10	21	0	0
双色牛肝菌近似种 <i>Boletus aff. bicolor</i>	1	9	0	0

... 待续 continued below

▼ 表 6. (续表)
Table 6. (continued)

误食类型 Ingestion types	事件数 Incidents	中毒人数 Patients	死亡人数 Deaths	死亡率 Fatality
粉黄肉牛肝菌(食用、神经) <i>Butyriboletus roseoflavus</i> E, P	2	16	0	0
黄盖堪多脆柄菇 <i>Candolleomyces candolleanus</i>	1	3	0	0
燕山堪多脆柄菇 <i>Candolleomyces yanshanensis</i>	1	3	0	0
多个杯伞科未定种 Clitocybaceae spp.	5	16	0	0
一个杯伞科或类脐菇科未定种 Clitocybaceae sp. or Omphalotaceae sp.	1	7	0	0
水粉杯伞 <i>Clitocybe nebularis</i>	1	1	0	0
白霜金钱菌 <i>Collybia dealbata</i>	2	3	0	0
潮湿金钱菌、洁小菇、毒灰盖杯伞、簇生垂幕菇(胃肠)、多环鳞伞(胃肠)、栎裸脚伞(胃肠)、橙黄乳菇(胃肠)、梭孢环柄菇(未定)、乳白小囊皮伞(未定)、一个蜡蘑属未定种(未定)、蜜环菌(食用)和皱盖囊皮伞(食用) <i>Collybia humida</i> , <i>Mycena pura</i> , <i>Spodocybe venenata</i> , <i>Hypholoma fasciculare</i> G, <i>Pholiota multicingulata</i> G, <i>Gymnopus dryophilus</i> G, <i>Lactarius citrinus</i> G, <i>Lepiota magnispora</i> U, <i>Cystoderma lactea</i> U, <i>Laccaria</i> sp. U, <i>Armillaria mellea</i> E & <i>Cystoderma amianthinum</i> E	1	20	0	0
近双足金钱菌 <i>Collybia subditopoda</i> (ined.)	2	6	0	0
亚热带金钱菌 <i>Collybia subtropica</i>	3	3	0	0
变色龙裸伞 <i>Gymnopilus dilepis</i>	24	61	0	0
鳞斑裸伞 <i>Gymnopilus lepidotus</i>	1	1	0	0
多个裸伞属未定种 <i>Gymnopilus</i> spp.	7	10	0	0
毒鹿花菌 <i>Gyromitra venenata</i>	3	5	0	0
赭色丝盖伞近似种 <i>Inocybe</i> aff. <i>assimilata</i>	1	1	0	0
钝凸丝盖伞近似种 <i>Inocybe</i> aff. <i>decemgibbosa</i>	1	2	0	0
欧石南丝盖伞近似种和暗褐红菇 <i>Inocybe</i> aff. <i>ericetorum</i> & <i>Russula insignis</i>	1	1	0	0
光盖丝盖伞近似种 <i>Inocybe</i> aff. <i>glabrodisca</i>	1	4	0	0
裂盖伞 <i>Pseudosperma rimosum</i>	2	4	0	0
晚秋丝盖伞 <i>Inocybe serotina</i>	3	5	0	0
晚秋丝盖伞和褐柄茸盖伞 <i>Inocybe serotina</i> & <i>Mallocybe fulvipes</i>	1	1	0	0

... 待续 continued below

▼ 表 6. (续表)
Table 6. (continued)

误食类型 Ingestion types	事件数 Incidents	中毒人数 Patients	死亡人数 Deaths	死亡率 Fatality
晚秋丝盖伞和小赭裂盖伞 <i>Inocybe serotina</i> & <i>Pseudosperma umbrinellum</i>	1	4	0	0
拟华美丝盖伞 <i>Inocybe splendentoides</i>	1	1	0	0
翘鳞蛋黄丝盖伞 <i>Inocybe squarrosolutea</i>	1	1	0	0
群生歧盖伞近似种 <i>Inosperma</i> aff. <i>gregarium</i>	1	1	0	0
海南歧盖伞 <i>Inosperma hainanense</i>	2	7	0	0
毒蝇歧盖伞 <i>Inosperma muscarium</i>	3	11	0	0
恶臭歧盖伞近似种 <i>Inosperma</i> aff. <i>virosum</i>	4	22	0	0
一个歧盖伞属未定种 <i>Inosperma</i> sp.	2	16	0	0
硫色灼孔菌复合群 <i>Laetiporus sulphureus</i> complex	1	1	0	0
兰茂牛肝菌(食用、神经) <i>Lanmaoa asiatica</i> E, P	17	22	0	0
兰茂牛肝菌(食用、神经)、日本网孢牛肝菌(胃肠)和新苦粉孢牛肝菌(胃肠) <i>Lanmaoa asiatica</i> E, P, <i>Heimioporus japonicus</i> G & <i>Tylophilus neofelleus</i> G	1	4	0	0
兰茂牛肝菌(食用、神经)、宽孢红孔牛肝菌(胃肠)、点柄乳牛肝菌(食用、胃肠)、象头山美柄牛肝菌(未定)和一个魔王牛肝菌属未定种(未定) <i>Lanmaoa asiatica</i> E, P, <i>Rubroboletus latisporus</i> G, <i>Suillus granulatus</i> E, G, <i>Caloboletus xiangtoushanensis</i> U & <i>Imperator</i> sp. U	1	3	0	0
兰茂牛肝菌(食用、神经)、宽孢红孔牛肝菌(胃肠)、铅紫异色牛肝菌近似种(胃肠)、新苦粉孢牛肝菌(胃肠)和一个新牛肝菌属未定种(未定) <i>Lanmaoa asiatica</i> E, P, <i>Rubroboletus latisporus</i> G, <i>Sutorius</i> aff. <i>eximius</i> G, <i>Tylophilus neofelleus</i> G & <i>Neoboletus</i> sp. U	1	3	0	0
多座线虫草 <i>Ophiocordyceps sobolifera</i>	1	1	0	0
双孢斑褶菇 <i>Panaeolus bisporus</i>	1	2	0	0
变蓝斑褶菇 <i>Panaeolus cyanescens</i>	3	5	0	0
粪生斑褶菇 <i>Panaeolus fimicola</i>	1	2	0	0
粪生斑褶菇和一个锥盖伞属未定种 <i>Panaeolus fimicola</i> & <i>Conocybe</i> sp.	1	2	0	0
褐红斑褶菇 <i>Panaeolus subbalteatus</i>	1	1	0	0
沙地裂盖伞 <i>Pseudosperma arenarium</i>	3	4	0	0

... 待续 continued below

▼ 表 6. (续表)
Table 6. (continued)

误食类型 Ingestion types	事件数 Incidents	中毒人数 Patients	死亡人数 Deaths	死亡率 Fatality
球基裂盖伞近似种 <i>Pseudosperma</i> aff. <i>bulbosissimum</i>	1	4	0	0
黄柄裂盖伞和假褪色丝盖伞 <i>Pseudosperma citrinostipes</i> & <i>Inocybe</i> aff. <i>pseudoreducta</i>	1	4	0	0
宴遇裂盖伞 <i>Pseudosperma conviviale</i>	1	2	0	0
三针松裂盖伞 <i>Pseudosperma triaciculare</i>	1	2	0	0
小赭裂盖伞 <i>Pseudosperma umbrinellum</i>	5	8	0	0
小赭裂盖伞和褐突茸盖伞 <i>Pseudosperma umbrinellum</i> & <i>Mallocybe fulvoumbonata</i>	1	2	0	0
小赭裂盖伞、黄盖堪多脆柄菇、西西里茸盖伞和沙丘滑锈伞(未定) <i>Pseudosperma umbrinellum</i> , <i>Candolleomyces candolleanus</i> , <i>Mallocybe siciliana</i> & <i>Hebeloma dunense</i> U	1	4	0	0
小赭裂盖伞、沙地裂盖伞、阿默兰丝盖伞、晚秋丝盖伞和沙丘滑锈伞(未定) <i>Pseudosperma umbrinellum</i> , <i>P. arenarium</i> , <i>Inocybe amelandica</i> , <i>I. serotina</i> & <i>Hebeloma dunense</i> U	1	2	0	0
乌莎裂盖伞和土星丝膜菌(未定) <i>Pseudosperma ushae</i> & <i>Cortinarius saturninus</i> U	1	2	0	0
云南裂盖伞 <i>Pseudosperma yunnanense</i>	1	1	0	0
云南裂盖伞、新苦粉孢牛肝菌(胃肠)和近裸拟金钱菌(未定) <i>Pseudosperma yunnanense</i> , <i>Tylopilus neofelleus</i> G & <i>Collybiopsis subnuda</i> U	1	6	0	0
一个裂盖伞属未定种 <i>Pseudosperma</i> sp.	1	2	0	0
古巴裸盖菇 <i>Psilocybe cubensis</i>	13	32	0	0
古巴裸盖菇和变红青褶伞(胃肠) <i>Psilocybe cubensis</i> & <i>Chlorophyllum hortense</i> G	1	11	0	0
古巴裸盖菇和大孢斑褶菇 <i>Psilocybe cubensis</i> & <i>Panaeolus papilionaceus</i>	1	6	0	0
喀拉拉裸盖菇 <i>Psilocybe keralensis</i>	1	1	0	0
卵囊裸盖菇 <i>Psilocybe ovoideocystidiata</i>	2	7	0	0
巴布亚裸盖菇 <i>Psilocybe papuana</i>	2	6	0	0
苏梅岛裸盖菇 <i>Psilocybe samuiensis</i>	4	9	0	0
泰绿裸盖菇 <i>Psilocybe thaiaerugineomaculans</i>	1	4	0	0
独角龙弯颈霉 <i>Tolypocladium dujiaolongae</i>	4	12	0	0

... 待续 continued below

▼ 表 6. (续表)
Table 6. (continued)

误食类型 Ingestion types	事件数 Incidents	中毒人数 Patients	死亡人数 Deaths	死亡率 Fatality
光过敏性皮炎型 Photosensitive dermatitis	5	10	0	0
叶状耳盘菌 <i>Cordierites frondosus</i>	5	10	0	0
未定型 Unclassified	107	276	0	0
变色蘑菇 <i>Agaricus albovariabilis</i>	1	1	0	0
北京蘑菇 <i>Agaricus beijingensis</i>	1	1	0	0
一个蘑菇属未定种和滴泪白环蘑 <i>Agaricus sp. & Leucoagaricus lacrymans</i>	1	1	0	0
一个蘑菇属未定种和一个红菇属未定种 <i>Agaricus sp. & Russula sp.</i>	1	1	0	0
一个蘑菇属未定种、肉桂色乳菇(食用)和东方小奥德蘑(食用) <i>Agaricus sp., Lactarius cinnamomeus E & Oudemansiella orientalis E</i>	1	1	0	0
一个蘑菇属未定种、鲜艳乳菇(食用)、绿桂红菇(食用)和小果蚁巢伞(食用) <i>Agaricus sp., Lactarius vividus E, Russula viridicinnamomea E & Termitomyces microcarpus E</i>	1	5	0	0
裹足鹅膏近似种和云杉粉褶蕈近似种 <i>Amanita aff. constricta & Entoloma aff. piceinum</i>	1	5	0	0
黄环鹅膏 <i>Amanita citrinoannulata</i>	1	4	0	0
显鳞鹅膏 <i>Amanita clarisquamosa</i>	1	3	0	0
灰褶鹅膏 <i>Amanita griseofolia</i>	1	4	0	0
黄边鹅膏 <i>Amanita hamadae</i>	1	1	0	0
一个鹅膏属未定种和白盖红菇(食用) <i>Amanita sp. & Russula leucocarpa E</i>	1	2	0	0
红铜色丝膜菌 <i>Cortinarius cupreorufus</i>	1	3	0	0
拟黄肉丝膜菌和中华丝膜菌(食用) <i>Cortinarius fulminoides & C. sinensis E</i>	1	4	0	0
土星丝膜菌 <i>Cortinarius saturninus</i>	1	1	0	0
相似丝膜菌、彝食黄肉牛肝菌(食用)、亚高山松苞菇(食用)和褐盖异色牛肝菌(食用、药用) <i>Cortinarius similis, Butyriboletus yicibus E, Catathelasma subalpinum E & Sutorius brunneissimus E, M</i>	1	3	0	0
云南蜡伞和假淡紫蜡伞 <i>Hygrophorus yunnanensis & H. pseudopurpurascens</i>	1	2	0	0
怀特蜡伞近似种、小尾马勃和纹缘大金钱菌 <i>Hygrophorus aff. whitei, Lycoperdon caudatum & Megacollybia marginata</i>	1	5	0	0

... 待续 continued below

▼ 表 6. (续表)
Table 6. (continued)

误食类型 Ingestion types	事件数 Incidents	中毒人数 Patients	死亡人数 Deaths	死亡率 Fatality
一个小蘑菇属未定种、血红园圃牛肝菌(食用)和拟篦边红菇(食用) <i>Micropsalliota</i> sp., <i>Hortiboletus rubellus</i> E & <i>Russula pectinatoides</i> E	1	2	0	0
一个小菇属未定种和大盖小皮伞(食用) <i>Mycena</i> sp. & <i>Marasmius maximus</i> E	1	1	0	0
囊泡新棱孔菌和薄皮干酪孔菌 <i>Neofavolus alveolaris</i> & <i>Tyromyces chioneus</i>	1	1	0	0
火色红孔牛肝菌、一个红孔牛肝菌属未定种、东方卢氏菇、一个魔王牛肝菌属未定种、一个美柄牛肝菌属未定种、一个丝盖伞属未定种、可爱红菇(胃肠)、兰茂牛肝菌(食用、神经)和绒紫红菇(食用) <i>Rubroboletus flammeus</i> , <i>Rubroboletus</i> sp., <i>Lulesia orientalis</i> , <i>Imperator</i> sp., <i>Caloboletus</i> sp., <i>Inocybe</i> sp., <i>Russula grata</i> G, <i>Lanmaoa asiatica</i> E, P & <i>Russula mariaae</i> E	1	2	0	0
多个红孔牛肝菌属未定种 <i>Rubroboletus</i> spp.	2	3	0	0
美丽红菇 <i>Russula pulchra</i>	1	3	0	0
一个红菇属未定种和白盖红菇(食用) <i>Russula</i> sp. & <i>Russula leucocarpa</i> E	1	4	0	0
一个红菇属未定种、密褶红菇(食用)和白盖红菇(食用) <i>Russula</i> sp., <i>R. densifolia</i> E & <i>R. leucocarpa</i> E	1	2	0	0
密鳞腐生鹅膏 <i>Sapromanita manicata</i>	1	1	0	0
长毛附毛孔菌 <i>Trichaptum byssogenum</i>	1	4	0	0
小孢疣钉菇近似种 <i>Turbinellus</i> aff. <i>parvisporus</i>	1	2	0	0
除独角龙弯颈霉(神经)、格纹鹅膏(神经)、黄环鹅膏、显鳞鹅膏、黄边鹅膏、花脸金钱菌(食用)、粗柄大口蘑(食用)和云南硬皮马勃(食用)外的其他蘑菇 (Li et al. (2020) 报道) Other mushrooms except <i>Tolypocladium dujiaolongae</i> P, <i>Amanita fritillaria</i> P, <i>A. citrinoannulata</i> , <i>A. clarisquamosa</i> , <i>A. hamadae</i> , <i>Collybia sordida</i> E, <i>Macrocybe crassa</i> E & <i>Scleroderma yunnanense</i> E (reported in Li et al. (2020))	12	46	0	0
林地蘑菇近似种(食用) <i>Agaricus</i> aff. <i>arvensis</i> E	1	1	0	0
巴西蘑菇(食用) <i>Agaricus blazei</i> E	1	2	0	0
四孢蘑菇(食用) <i>Agaricus campestris</i> E	3	3	0	0
赭鳞蘑菇(食用) <i>Agaricus subrufescens</i> E	1	4	0	0
高大鹅膏近似种(食用) <i>Amanita</i> aff. <i>princeps</i> E	1	2	0	0
假高大鹅膏(食用) <i>Amanita pseudoprinceps</i> E	2	3	0	0
高卢蜜环菌(食用) <i>Armillaria gallica</i> E	1	3	0	0

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▼ 表 6. (续表)
Table 6. (continued)

误食类型 Ingestion types	事件数 Incidents	中毒人数 Patients	死亡人数 Deaths	死亡率 Fatality
蜜环菌(食用) <i>Armillaria mellea</i> E	1	3	0	0
白牛肝菌(食用) <i>Boletus bainiugan</i> E	1	2	0	0
白牛肝菌(食用)和网盖牛肝菌(食用) <i>Boletus bainiugan</i> E & <i>B. reticuloceps</i> E	1	28	0	0
彝食黄肉牛肝菌(食用) <i>Butyriboletus yicibus</i> E	2	6	0	0
杯形秃马勃(食用、药用) <i>Calvatia cyathiformis</i> E, M	1	1	0	0
大秃马勃(食用、药用) <i>Calvatia gigantea</i> E, M	1	1	0	0
紫丁金钱菌(食用、药用) <i>Collybia nuda</i> E, M	1	4	0	0
花脸金钱菌(食用) <i>Collybia sordida</i> E	1	1	0	0
雪白拟鬼伞(食用) <i>Coprinopsis nivea</i> E	1	3	0	0
毛头鬼伞(食用) <i>Coprinus comatus</i> E	2	3	0	0
中华丝膜菌(食用) <i>Cortinarius sinensis</i> E	2	4	0	0
隐孔菌(药用) <i>Cryptoporus volvatus</i> M	1	1	0	0
酒红蜡蘑(食用) <i>Laccaria vinaceoavellanea</i> E	1	2	0	0
肉桂色乳菇(食用) <i>Lactarius cinnamomeus</i> E	1	2	0	0
薄囊多汁乳菇(食用) <i>Lactifluus tenuicystidiatus</i> E	1	2	0	0
巴氏白环蘑(食用) <i>Leucoagaricus barssii</i> E	1	2	0	0
网纹马勃复合群(食用、药用) <i>Lycoperdon perlatum</i> complex E, M	1	1	0	0
粗柄大口蘑(食用) <i>Macrocybe crassa</i> E	2	3	0	0
黄孔新牛肝菌(食用) <i>Neoboletus flavidus</i> E	2	2	0	0
黄孔新牛肝菌(食用)和大孢地花孔菌(食用) <i>Neoboletus flavidus</i> E & <i>Albatrellus ellisii</i> E	1	2	0	0
虎皮韧伞(食用) <i>Lentinus tigrinus</i> E	1	1	0	0
巨大侧耳(食用) <i>Pleurotus giganteus</i> E	1	4	0	0
泡状鳞伞(食用、药用) <i>Pholiota spumosa</i> E, M	1	3	0	0
彩色豆马勃复合群(食用、药用) <i>Pisolithus arhizus</i> complex E, M	1	4	0	0

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▼ 表 6. (续表)
Table 6. (continued)

误食类型 Ingestion types	事件数 Incidents	中毒人数 Patients	死亡人数 Deaths	死亡率 Fatality
糙皮侧耳(食用) <i>Pleurotus ostreatus</i> E	1	1	0	0
肺形侧耳(食用) <i>Pleurotus pulmonarius</i> E	1	1	0	0
褐网柄牛肝菌(食用) <i>Retiboletus fuscus</i> E	1	2	0	0
壳状红菇(食用)和云南蜡蘑(食用) <i>Russula crustosa</i> E & <i>Laccaria yunnanensis</i> E	1	6	0	0
密褶红菇(食用) <i>Russula densifolia</i> E	1	2	0	0
白盖红菇(食用) <i>Russula leucocarpa</i> E	1	3	0	0
绿桂红菇近似种(食用) <i>Russula</i> aff. <i>viridicinnamomea</i> E	1	4	0	0
裂褶菌(食用、药用)、毛栓孔菌(药用)和乳白耙齿菌(药用) <i>Schizophyllum commune</i> E, M, <i>Trametes hirsuta</i> M & <i>Irpex lacteus</i> M	1	1	0	0
云南硬皮马勃(食用) <i>Scleroderma yunnanense</i> E	6	16	0	0
皱环球盖菇(食用) <i>Stropharia rugosoannulata</i> E	3	3	0	0
云南蚁巢伞(食用) <i>Termitomyces yunnanensis</i> E	1	1	0	0
毛栓孔菌(药用) <i>Trametes hirsuta</i> M	1	1	0	0
棕灰口蘑(食用) <i>Tricholoma terreum</i> E	6	10	0	0
细绒盖牛肝菌(食用) <i>Xerocomus parvulus</i> E	1	4	0	0

▼ 表 7. 2020–2023 年中国各省级行政区蘑菇中毒事件的基本数据 (2019 年无此数据); 按中毒人数降序排序.

Table 7. Basic data of mushroom poisoning incidents in each province-level administrative division in China from 2020 to 2023 (no such data for 2019), in descending order of Patients.

省级行政区 Province-level administrative divisions	事件数 Incidents	中毒人数 Patients	死亡人数 Deaths	死亡率 Fatality
湖南 Hunan	571	1277	12	0.94%
云南 Yunnan	352	1073	21	1.96%
贵州 Guizhou	160	535	13	2.43%
四川 Sichuan	179	485	5	1.03%
广西 Guangxi	78	318	8	2.52%

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▼ 表 7. (续表)
Table 7. (continued)

省级行政区 Province-level administrative divisions	事件数 Incidents	中毒人数 Patients	死亡人数 Deaths	死亡率 Fatality
重庆 Chongqing	100	273	3	1.10%
浙江 Zhejiang	102	221	0	0
福建 Fujian	71	178	1	0.56%
广东 Guangdong	66	151	14	9.27%
湖北 Hubei	67	142	1	0.70%
宁夏 Ningxia	53	106	1	0.94%
安徽 Anhui	26	79	0	0
山东 Shandong	27	72	3	4.17%
江苏 Jiangsu	24	70	0	0
河北 Hebei	17	59	0	0
海南 Hainan	14	58	0	0
江西 Jiangxi	25	39	1	2.56%
北京 Beijing	11	39	1	2.56%
江苏 Jiangsu	13	33	0	0
河南 Henan	8	14	1	7.14%
山西 Shanxi	5	11	2	18.18%
内蒙古 Nei Mongol	4	8	1	12.50%
新疆 Xinjiang	2	8	0	0
辽宁 Liaoning	2	7	0	0
陕西 Shaanxi	2	4	0	0
甘肃 Gansu	2	5	0	0
西藏 Xizang	3	3	1	33.33%
吉林 Jilin	2	3	0	0
上海 Shanghai	2	2	0	0

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▼ 表 7. (续表)
Table 7. (continued)

省级行政区 Province-level administrative divisions	事件数 Incidents	中毒人数 Patients	死亡人数 Deaths	死亡率 Fatality
黑龙江 Heilongjiang	1	2	0	0
天津 Tianjin	1	2	0	0
香港 Hong Kong	0	0	0	0
澳门 Macau	0	0	0	0
青海 Qinghai	0	0	0	0
台湾 Taiwan	0	0	0	0

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Availability of data and materials

The specimens cited in this study were deposited in Kun L. Yang's private herbarium (HTBM) and the Herbarium of Cryptogams, Kunming Institute of Botany, Chinese Academy of Sciences (HKAS).

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Additional notes (if necessary)

Posted as the celebration of my 20th birthday (*~*~*) although it's been few days later. Thanks for the kind cooperation of my girlfriend Jia Y. Lin and our enthusiastic colleague Dr. Hai-Jiao Li!